

Axiomatic Construction of First Quantization and Deduction of the Schrödinger Equation - A theory for analytical Hamiltonians

Pedro Rodrigo Arango Zuñiga

Affiliation: Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos

E-mail address: `pedro.arangoz@unmsm.edu.pe`

Summary

In this work, a formulation of non-relativistic quantum mechanics is developed from the first four postulates, taken as axioms, by constructing the entire theory with additional definitions and using the abstract framework of kets and linear operators defined on a Hilbert space of quantum states. Within this axiomatic setting, the canonical commutation relations, the correspondence between commutators and Poisson brackets in the classical limit, and the identification of the time-evolution generator with the classical Hamiltonian emerge naturally.

The central idea of this approach is that the internal consistency of Schrödinger's theory relies on the analytical character of the Hamiltonian. The analyticity condition guarantees the differentiability required for operator expansions, ensures the validity of the canonical relations, and underpins the equivalence between quantum and classical mechanics at the level of expectation values. This perspective suggests that quantum mechanics is, in essence, a theory intrinsically defined for analytical Hamiltonians, which may explain the inconsistencies that arise when extending the formalism to non-analytical or singular systems.

Finally, the generalized Schrödinger equation for an arbitrary number of degrees of freedom is deduced within this framework, showing that the system's function naturally acquires the structure of a wave function representing the wave-particle duality. In this way, the abstract operator formalism and the physical representation of quantum mechanics are unified under a single, analytically consistent foundation

1. Introduction

Non-relativistic quantum mechanics arose from the seminal works of Planck, Bohr, de Broglie, Heisenberg, and Schrödinger, whose wave equation was heuristically derived from the Hamilton-Jacobi formalism. However, the theory was not originally established from a strict mathematical foundation, leaving the consistency and scope of its postulates open to question. Also, it is known that non-analytical Hamiltonians—such as those containing discontinuous, singular, or piecewise-defined potentials—lead to well-known difficulties: ill-defined commutators, non-unitary evolutions, and ambiguities in the boundary conditions of the Schrödinger equation.

Therefore, this work develops a logical and mathematically rigorous formulation based on analytical operators, emphasizing that the internal consistency of Schrödinger's theory depends on the analyticity of the Hamiltonian.

2. The first four axiomatic postulates

2.1. Postulate I

The state of every quantum system is an abstract vector $|\Psi\rangle$ which belongs to a complex, separable Hilbert space H .

2.2. Postulate II

The Physical observables \hat{A} are linear hermitian operators, whose eigenvectors $|a_n\rangle$ form a basis in H . That is, if $\hat{A}|a_n\rangle = \lambda_n|a_n\rangle \forall n \in S$ then any state can be written as:

$$|\Psi\rangle = \sum_{n \in S} c_n |a_n\rangle$$

where $\{|a_n\rangle\}$ is an orthonormal basis, which allows obtaining the projection $c_n = \langle a_n | \Psi \rangle$ since $\langle a_n | a_m \rangle = \delta_{nm}$.

It is important to point out that the set S is not exclusively finite and discrete, but rather it may be continuous, which implies that in the latter case one has:

$$|\Psi\rangle = \int_{n \in S} c_n |a_n\rangle d\lambda_n$$

where the orthogonality is now given by a Dirac delta:

$$\langle a_n | a_m \rangle = \delta(\lambda_n - \lambda_m).$$

2.3. Postulate III

The probability that the observable \hat{A} measures the value λ_n on the system $|\Psi\rangle$ is given by $|c_n|^2$. That is:

$$P_{\lambda_n} = |c_n|^2 = |\langle a_n | \Psi \rangle|^2$$

Therefore, the expectation value of \hat{A} is:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{A} \rangle &= \sum_{n \in S} \lambda_n P_{\lambda_n} = \sum_{n \in S} \lambda_n |c_n|^2 \\ \langle \hat{A} \rangle &= \sum_{n \in S} c_n^* \lambda_n c_n = \sum_{m \in S} \sum_{n \in S} \langle a_m | c_m^* \lambda_n c_n | a_n \rangle = \sum_{m \in S} \sum_{n \in S} \langle a_m | c_m^* \hat{A} c_n | a_n \rangle \\ &\Rightarrow \langle \hat{A} \rangle = \langle \Psi | \hat{A} | \Psi \rangle \end{aligned}$$

This can be readily verified for the case of a continuous spectrum of values.

With this, the uncertainty of a measurement is also defined as the standard deviation:

$$\Delta A = \sqrt{\langle \hat{A}^2 \rangle - \langle \hat{A} \rangle^2}$$

2.4. Postulate IV

The system collapses instantaneously once the measurement is performed with the observable \hat{A} . That is, if at $t = T$ the measurement is carried out with the operator \hat{A} , then the evolution of the system takes the following form:

$$|\Psi\rangle = \begin{cases} \sum_{n \in S} c_n |a_n\rangle, & 0 \leq t < T \\ |a_m\rangle, & t = T \end{cases}$$

Note that the basis states $|a_n\rangle$ and the coefficients c_n generally depend on time, and their evolution will be smooth throughout the entire interval $[0, T]$. It is precisely in this type of interval that the Schrödinger equation comes into play, dictating the deterministic evolution of the system.

3. Elements of Quantum Theory

3.1. Construction of the Time Evolution Operator

The evolution of the state from t_0 to t is defined as:

$$|\psi(t)\rangle = \hat{U}(t, t_0)|\psi(t_0)\rangle$$

Where $\hat{U}(t, t_0)$ is the time evolution operator, and no assumption is made that $t > t_0$.

Proposition 1: $\hat{U}(t_0, t_0) = I \quad \forall t_0$

Dem: $|\psi(t_0)\rangle = \hat{U}(t_0, t_0)|\psi(t_0)\rangle \quad \forall t_0 \Rightarrow \hat{U}(t_0, t_0) = I$

Proposition 2: $\hat{U}(t_2, t_1)\hat{U}(t_1, t_0) = \hat{U}(t_2, t_0)$

Dem: $\hat{U}(t_2, t_1)\hat{U}(t_1, t_0)|\psi(t_0)\rangle = \hat{U}(t_2, t_1)|\psi(t_1)\rangle = |\psi(t_2)\rangle = \hat{U}(t_2, t_0)|\psi(t_0)\rangle \quad \forall t_0$
 $\Rightarrow \hat{U}(t_2, t_1)\hat{U}(t_1, t_0) = \hat{U}(t_2, t_0)$

Proposition 3: $\hat{U}^{-1}(t, t_0) = \hat{U}(t_0, t)$

Dem: By Prop. 2 $\hat{U}(t_0, t)\hat{U}(t, t_0) = \hat{U}(t_0, t_0) = I \quad \forall t, t_0$

If we set $\hat{U}(t, t) = \hat{U}(t, t_0)\hat{U}(t_0, t)$, then in the same manner

$I = \hat{U}(t, t_0)\hat{U}(t_0, t) \quad \forall t, t_0 \Rightarrow \hat{U}(t_0, t) = \hat{U}^{-1}(t, t_0)$

Proposition 4: $\hat{U}^\dagger = \hat{U}^{-1}$

Dem: From Postulate III, consider the operator $\hat{A} = I$. It follows that $\langle I \rangle = 1 = \langle \Psi | I | \Psi \rangle = \langle \Psi | \Psi \rangle$. Thus, the norm is a temporal invariant, and we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi(t) | \psi(t) \rangle &= \langle \psi(t_0) | \psi(t_0) \rangle \Rightarrow \langle \psi(t_0) | \hat{U}^\dagger(t, t_0) \hat{U}(t, t_0) | \psi(t_0) \rangle = \langle \psi(t_0) | \psi(t_0) \rangle \quad \forall t, t_0 \\ &\Rightarrow \hat{U}^\dagger \hat{U} = \hat{U} \hat{U}^\dagger = I \Rightarrow \hat{U}^\dagger = \hat{U}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

The quantum operator \hat{G} , also referred to as the generator, is associated as follows:

$$\hat{U}(t + \Delta t, t) \approx I + \Delta t \hat{G} \quad ; \quad \Delta t \approx 0$$

It is implicitly understood that, in general, this generator depends on time; that is, $\hat{G} = \hat{G}(t)$.

We shall see whether it is well defined. Let there be two successive evolutions with increments Δt_1 and Δt_2 , then the first-order approximation is:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{U}(t + \Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2, t + \Delta t_1)\hat{U}(t + \Delta t_1, t) &\approx (I + \Delta t_2\hat{G}_1)(I + \Delta t_1\hat{G}) \\ &\approx I + \Delta t_1\hat{G} + \Delta t_2\hat{G}_1 + \underbrace{\Delta t_2\Delta t_1\hat{G}_1\hat{G}}_{\approx 0} \approx I + \Delta t_1\hat{G} + \Delta t_2\hat{G}_1\end{aligned}$$

Since $\hat{G}_1 = \hat{G}(t + \Delta t_1) \approx \hat{G} + \Delta t_1 \frac{\partial \hat{G}}{\partial t}$, then:

$$\hat{U}(t + \Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2, t + \Delta t_1)\hat{U}(t + \Delta t_1, t) \approx I + \Delta t_1\hat{G} + \Delta t_2\hat{G} + \underbrace{\Delta t_2\Delta t_1 \frac{\partial \hat{G}}{\partial t}}_{\approx 0}$$

$$\hat{U}(t + \Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2, t + \Delta t_1)\hat{U}(t + \Delta t_1, t) \approx I + (\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2)\hat{G}$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{U}(t + \Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2, t + \Delta t_1)\hat{U}(t + \Delta t_1, t) = \hat{U}(t + \Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2, t)$$

We observe that coherence with Property 2 is maintained.

Since $\hat{U}^\dagger = \hat{U}^{-1}$, then we have:

$$\hat{U}^\dagger(t + \Delta t, t) = \hat{U}^{-1}(t + \Delta t, t) = \hat{U}(t, t + \Delta t) = \hat{U}((t + \Delta t) - \Delta t, t + \Delta t)$$

Which, to first order, implies:

$$I + \Delta t\hat{G}^\dagger \approx I - \Delta t\hat{G}_1 \approx I - \Delta t\hat{G}$$

Therefore, the generator must be defined with the property of being **anti-Hermitian**:

Proposition 5: $\hat{G}^\dagger = -\hat{G}$

Now, applying an infinitesimal time evolution to an arbitrary state $|\psi(t)\rangle$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{U}(t + \Delta t, t)|\psi(t)\rangle &= |\psi(t + \Delta t)\rangle \\ \Rightarrow (I + \Delta t\hat{G})|\psi(t)\rangle &\approx |\psi(t + \Delta t)\rangle \\ \Rightarrow |\psi(t)\rangle + \Delta t\hat{G}|\psi(t)\rangle &\approx |\psi(t + \Delta t)\rangle \\ \Rightarrow \hat{G}|\psi(t)\rangle &\approx \frac{|\psi(t + \Delta t)\rangle - |\psi(t)\rangle}{\Delta t}\end{aligned}$$

Taking the limit, one obtains the equality:

$$\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \hat{G}|\psi(t)\rangle = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{|\psi(t + \Delta t)\rangle - |\psi(t)\rangle}{\Delta t}$$

Thus, the following important relation holds:

$$\hat{G}|\psi(t)\rangle = \frac{\partial|\psi(t)\rangle}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

Now, replacing the time evolution operator, we obtain:

$$\hat{G}\hat{U}(t, t_0)|\psi(t_0)\rangle = \frac{\partial\hat{U}(t, t_0)}{\partial t}|\psi(t_0)\rangle \quad \forall t_0$$

Then the following differential equation must hold:

$$\hat{G}(t)\hat{U}(t, t_0) = \frac{\partial\hat{U}(t, t_0)}{\partial t}$$

Integrating it, we have:

$$\int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(t_1)\hat{U}(t_1, t_0) dt_1 = \int_{t_0}^t \frac{\partial\hat{U}(t_1, t_0)}{\partial t_1} dt_1 = \hat{U}(t, t_0) - I$$

It is:

$$\hat{U}(t, t_0) = I + \int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(t_1)\hat{U}(t_1, t_0) dt_1$$

But:

$$\hat{U}(t_1, t_0) = I + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \hat{G}(t_2)\hat{U}(t_2, t_0) dt_2$$

Then replacing:

$$\hat{U}(t, t_0) = I + \int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(t_1) dt_1 + \int_{t_0}^t \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \hat{G}(t_1)\hat{G}(t_2)\hat{U}(t_2, t_0) dt_2 dt_1$$

Analogously, by continuing the substitutions indefinitely, one obtains:

$$\hat{U}(t, t_0) = I + \int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(t_1) dt_1 + \int_{t_0}^t \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \hat{G}(t_1)\hat{G}(t_2) dt_2 dt_1 + \int_{t_0}^t \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \int_{t_0}^{t_2} \hat{G}(t_1)\hat{G}(t_2)\hat{G}(t_3) dt_3 dt_2 dt_1 + \dots$$

The third term can be set equal to:

$$\int_{t_0}^t \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \hat{G}(t_1)\hat{G}(t_2) dt_2 dt_1 = \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_0}^t \int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(t_1)\hat{G}(t_2) dt_2 dt_1$$

Which is obtained after permuting t_1 and t_2 , as shown in the figure.

Figura 1: Diagram showing the permutation of t_1 and t_2 .

Where it is used that the integrand has symmetry under pairwise permutations.

Analogously, it can be shown that in the remaining terms all possible pairs of dummy variables can be permuted and added, which yields the general rule:

$$\int_{t_0}^t \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \cdots \int_{t_0}^{t_{n-1}} \hat{G}(t_1) \hat{G}(t_2) \cdots \hat{G}(t_n) dt_n \cdots dt_2 dt_1 = \frac{1}{n!} \int_{t_0}^t \int_{t_0}^t \cdots \int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(t_1) \hat{G}(t_2) \cdots \hat{G}(t_n) dt_n \cdots dt_2 dt_1$$

Which, in turn, may be separated as:

$$\int_{t_0}^t \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \cdots \int_{t_0}^{t_{n-1}} \hat{G}(t_1) \hat{G}(t_2) \cdots \hat{G}(t_n) dt_n \cdots dt_2 dt_1 = \frac{1}{n!} \left(\int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(\tau) d\tau \right)^n$$

Accordingly, substituting each term, one obtains:

$$\hat{U}(t, t_0) = I + \frac{1}{1!} \int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(\tau) d\tau + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(\tau) d\tau \right)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} \left(\int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(\tau) d\tau \right)^3 + \dots$$

Then the time evolution operator is given by:

$$\hat{U}(t, t_0) = \exp \left(\int_{t_0}^t \hat{G}(\tau) d\tau \right) \quad (2)$$

With this, we have obtained the time evolution operator as an exclusive function of its generator.

3.2. Temporal Derivative of the Expectation Value of an Observable

Let us take the derivative of the expectation value of an observable:

$$\frac{d\langle \hat{A} \rangle}{dt} = \frac{d\langle \psi(t) | \hat{A} | \psi(t) \rangle}{dt} = \frac{d\langle \psi(t_0) | \hat{U}^\dagger \hat{A} \hat{U} | \psi(t_0) \rangle}{dt}$$

$$\frac{d\langle \hat{A} \rangle}{dt} = \langle \psi(t_0) | \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\hat{U}^\dagger \hat{A} \hat{U}] | \psi(t_0) \rangle$$

Since

$$\frac{\partial \hat{U}}{\partial t} = \hat{G}\hat{U}$$

Then

$$\frac{\partial \hat{U}^\dagger}{\partial t} = -\hat{U}^\dagger \hat{G}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\hat{U}^\dagger \hat{A} \hat{U}] = -\hat{U}^\dagger \hat{G} \hat{A} \hat{U} + \hat{U}^\dagger \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial t} \hat{U} + \hat{U}^\dagger \hat{A} \hat{G} \hat{U}$$

Thus we have:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\hat{U}^\dagger \hat{A} \hat{U}] = \hat{U}^\dagger \left(-\hat{G} \hat{A} + \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial t} + \hat{A} \hat{G} \right) \hat{U} = \hat{U}^\dagger \left([\hat{A}, \hat{G}] + \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial t} \right) \hat{U}$$

$$\frac{d\langle \hat{A} \rangle}{dt} = \langle \psi(t_0) | \hat{U}^\dagger \left([\hat{A}, \hat{G}] + \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial t} \right) \hat{U} | \psi(t_0) \rangle$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{d\langle \hat{A} \rangle}{dt} = \langle \psi(t) | \left([\hat{A}, \hat{G}] + \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial t} \right) | \psi(t) \rangle$$

Finally, we have another fundamental relation:

$$\frac{d\langle \hat{A} \rangle}{dt} = \langle [\hat{A}, \hat{G}] \rangle + \left\langle \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial t} \right\rangle \quad (3)$$

3.3. Construction of the Position Observable

We shall first deal with the one-dimensional case and then easily generalize it. We define the position operator \hat{X} as an observable that gives the position or the value of a certain spatial degree of freedom of the system. Its eigenvectors are represented as $|x\rangle$, which corresponds to the instantaneous and pointlike occurrence of a particle at that coordinate.

It is clear that the spectrum of values of this observable is continuous; therefore, according to Postulate II, we have:

$$\hat{X}|x\rangle = x|x\rangle$$

And the quantum state of a system expressed in this basis is:

$$|\psi\rangle = \int c(x')|x'\rangle dx'$$

The orthonormality relation of the eigenstates is:

$$\langle x|x'\rangle = \delta(x - x')$$

And the coefficients $C(x)$ are given by the function:

$$C(x) = \langle x|\psi\rangle$$

Then, as dictated by the second postulate, $|C(x)|^2$ will represent the probability density of finding the particle in the infinitesimal interval $[x, x + dx]$.

In the final part of this work, it will be shown that this function is indeed a wave function, but for the moment it will be treated as a function of the system.

Substituting this function into the system's *ket*:

$$|\psi\rangle = \int |x'\rangle \langle x'|\psi\rangle dx' = \int |x'\rangle \langle x'|dx'|\psi\rangle$$

Then the identity operator in this basis is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{I} = \int |\mathbf{x}'\rangle \langle \mathbf{x}'|d\mathbf{x}' \quad (4)$$

If the system possesses N spatial degrees of freedom, the position eigenvector is given by the Kronecker product in the Hilbert space of the N *kets* $|x_i\rangle$, namely:

$$|\vec{r}\rangle = |x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_N\rangle$$

And the position operator will be a matrix arrangement given by:

$$\hat{R} = (\hat{X}_1^*, \hat{X}_2^*, \dots, \hat{X}_N^*)$$

with

$$\hat{X}_j^* = I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I \quad \forall 1 \leq j \leq N$$

With this, the orthonormality relation is:

$$\langle \vec{r}|\vec{r}'\rangle = (\langle x_1|\otimes \langle x_2|\otimes \cdots \otimes \langle x_N|)(|x'_1\rangle \otimes |x'_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x'_N\rangle)$$

$$\langle \vec{r}|\vec{r}'\rangle = \langle x_1|x'_1\rangle \otimes \langle x_2|x'_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes \langle x_N|x'_N\rangle$$

Which, being simple scalars, reduce to:

$$\langle \vec{r}|\vec{r}'\rangle = \langle x_1|x'_1\rangle \langle x_2|x'_2\rangle \cdots \langle x_N|x'_N\rangle = \delta(x_1 - x'_1)\delta(x_2 - x'_2) \cdots \delta(x_N - x'_N)$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle \vec{r}|\vec{r}'\rangle = \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}')$$

And the eigenvalues are:

$$\hat{R}|\vec{r}\rangle = (\hat{X}_1^*, \hat{X}_2^*, \dots, \hat{X}_N^*)|\vec{r}\rangle$$

Since $\hat{X}_j^*|\vec{r}\rangle = (I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I)(|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_N\rangle)$ it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{X}_j^*|\vec{r}\rangle &= |x_1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j|x_j\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_N\rangle \\ \Rightarrow \hat{X}_j^*|\vec{r}\rangle &= |x_1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes x_j|x_j\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_N\rangle = x_j|\vec{r}\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Then:

$$\hat{R}|\vec{r}\rangle = (x_1|\vec{r}\rangle, x_2|\vec{r}\rangle, \dots, x_N|\vec{r}\rangle) = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N)|\vec{r}\rangle$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{R}|\vec{r}\rangle = \vec{r}|\vec{r}\rangle$$

And now, the state $|\psi\rangle$ is weighted in the phase space of positions with the measure $dx_N \dots dx_2 dx_1 = d^N \vec{r}$, so that we have:

$$|\psi\rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} C(\vec{r}') |\vec{r}'\rangle d^N \vec{r}'$$

With this, one can readily show that the coefficients $C(\vec{r})$ and the identity operator I are:

$$C(\vec{r}) = \langle \vec{r} | \psi \rangle \quad \text{and} \quad I = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\vec{r}'\rangle \langle \vec{r}'| d^N \vec{r}'$$

From this we can conclude that the probability density $|C(\vec{r})|^2$ is a density in the phase space of the physical system, just as it appears in statistical physics. From now on, we shall denote the function $C(\vec{r})$ by $\psi(\vec{r})$.

One last property of this function is that the normalization condition implies:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi | \psi \rangle &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \langle \psi | \vec{r}' \rangle \langle \vec{r}' | \psi \rangle d^N \vec{r}' \\ 1 &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \psi^*(\vec{r}') \psi(\vec{r}') d^N \vec{r}' \\ \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\psi(\vec{r}')|^2 d^N \vec{r}' &= 1 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

An interesting result, which will be used hereafter, is the representation in position space of the measurement of \hat{A} on the quantum state $|\psi\rangle$, that is, $\langle \vec{r}' | \hat{A} | \psi \rangle$:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \vec{r}' | \hat{A} | \psi \rangle &= \langle \vec{r}' | \hat{A} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\vec{r}''\rangle \langle \vec{r}'' | \psi \rangle d^N \vec{r}'' = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \langle \vec{r}' | \hat{A} | \vec{r}'' \rangle \psi(\vec{r}'') d^N \vec{r}'' \\ \langle \vec{r}' | \hat{A} | \psi \rangle &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \langle \vec{r}' | \hat{A} | \vec{r}'' \rangle \psi(\vec{r}'') d^N \vec{r}'' \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

3.4. Construction of the Spatial Translation Operator

3.4.1. Definition and Properties in the One-Dimensional Case

In one dimension, the one-parameter spatial translation operator is defined as:

$$\hat{T}(x_0) |x\rangle = |x + x_0\rangle$$

Which translates any coordinate by the amount x_0 . The properties of this operator are:

Proposition 6: $\hat{T}(0) = I$

Dem: $\hat{T}(0) |x\rangle = |x + 0\rangle = |x\rangle \quad \forall |x\rangle \Rightarrow \hat{T}(0) = I$

Proposition 7: $\hat{T}(a_1) \hat{T}(a_2) = \hat{T}(a_1 + a_2)$

Dem: $\hat{T}(a_1) \hat{T}(a_2) |x\rangle = \hat{T}(a_1) |x + a_2\rangle = |x + a_1 + a_2\rangle = \hat{T}(a_1 + a_2) |x\rangle \forall |x\rangle$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{T}(a_1) \hat{T}(a_2) = \hat{T}(a_1 + a_2)$$

It should be noted that this property is symmetric.

Proposition 8: $\hat{T}^{-1}(x_0) = \hat{T}(-x_0)$

Dem: By the Prop 6 and 7 we have $\hat{T}(-x_0)\hat{T}(x_0) = \hat{T}(x_0)\hat{T}(-x_0) = \hat{T}(x_0 - x_0) = \hat{T}(0) = I \quad \forall x_0$
 $\Rightarrow \hat{T}^{-1}(x_0) = \hat{T}(-x_0)$

Proposition 9: $\hat{T}^\dagger = \hat{T}^{-1}$

Dem: Since $\langle x + x_0 | x' + x_0 \rangle = \delta(x + x_0 - (x' + x_0)) = \delta(x - x') = \langle x | x' \rangle$

$$\Rightarrow \langle x | \hat{T}^\dagger \hat{T} | x' \rangle = \langle x | \hat{T} | x' \rangle = \langle x | x' \rangle \quad \forall |x\rangle, |x'\rangle \Rightarrow \hat{T}^\dagger \hat{T} = I \Rightarrow \hat{T}^\dagger = \hat{T}^{-1}$$

An immediate consequence of this property is that any quantum state remains normalized before and after the translation, as shown below:

$$\langle \psi | \hat{T}^\dagger \hat{T} | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | I | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | \psi \rangle = 1$$

3.4.2. The Spatial Translation Generator

We associate the generator \hat{d} when Δx is very small, as follows:

$$\hat{T}(\Delta x) \approx I + \Delta x \hat{d}$$

We check whether it is well defined. Evidently, Property 6 is satisfied, whereas for Property 7 we proceed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}(\Delta a_1) \hat{T}(\Delta a_2) &\approx (I + \Delta a_1 \hat{d})(I + \Delta a_2 \hat{d}) = I + (\Delta a_1 + \Delta a_2) \hat{d} + \underbrace{\Delta a_1 \Delta a_2 \hat{d}^2}_{\approx 0} \\ &\Rightarrow \hat{T}(\Delta a_1) \hat{T}(\Delta a_2) \approx I + (\Delta a_1 + \Delta a_2) \hat{d} \approx \hat{T}(\Delta a_1 + \Delta a_2) \end{aligned}$$

Checking its verification, then to verify Property 8 it is sufficient to take $\Delta a_2 = -\Delta a_1$. Finally, to verify Property 9, we substitute:

$$\hat{T}^\dagger(\Delta x) = \hat{T}^{-1}(\Delta x) = \hat{T}(-\Delta x) \Rightarrow I + \Delta x \hat{d}^\dagger \approx I - \Delta x \hat{d}$$

Thus, \hat{d} is to be defined as an anti-Hermitian operator, namely:

Proposition 10: $\hat{d}^\dagger = -\hat{d}$

Now, consider a small increment on a *ket* $|x\rangle$; then:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}(\Delta x) |x\rangle &\approx (I + \Delta x \hat{d}) |x\rangle \Rightarrow |x + \Delta x\rangle \approx |x\rangle + \Delta x \hat{d} |x\rangle \\ &\Rightarrow \hat{d} |x\rangle \approx \frac{|x + \Delta x\rangle - |x\rangle}{\Delta x} \end{aligned}$$

In the limit of this relation, the following equality is obtained:

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \hat{d} |x\rangle = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{|x + \Delta x\rangle - |x\rangle}{\Delta x} \Rightarrow \hat{d} |x\rangle = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} |x\rangle$$

But $|x\rangle = \hat{T}(x) |0\rangle$, then:

$$\hat{d}\hat{T}(x)|0\rangle = \frac{\partial\hat{T}(x)}{\partial x}|0\rangle \Rightarrow \hat{d}\hat{T}(x) = \frac{\partial\hat{T}(x)}{\partial x}$$

We integrate this last relation from 0 to x . But first, we must note that the generator \hat{d} is clearly an operator independent of x or Δx , therefore we have:

$$\hat{T}(x) = I + \hat{d} \int_0^x \hat{T}(u_1) du_1$$

Since

$$\hat{T}(u_1) = I + \hat{d} \int_0^{u_1} \hat{T}(u_2) du_2$$

Replacing:

$$\hat{T}(x) = I + \hat{d} \int_0^x du_1 + \hat{d}^2 \int_0^x \int_0^{u_1} \hat{T}(u_2) du_2 du_1$$

By performing this iteration indefinitely, we obtain:

$$\hat{T}(x) = I + \hat{d} \int_0^x du_1 + \hat{d}^2 \int_0^x \int_0^{u_1} du_2 du_1 + \hat{d}^3 \int_0^x \int_0^{u_1} \int_0^{u_2} du_3 du_2 du_1 + \dots$$

$$\hat{T}(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \hat{d}^n \int_0^x \int_0^{u_1} \dots \int_0^{u_{n-1}} du_n \dots du_2 du_1 = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \hat{d}^n C_n$$

Let us find the coefficients C_n :

$$C_n = \int_0^x \dots \int_0^{u_{n-1}} du_n \dots du_1 = \int_0^x \dots \int_0^{u_{n-2}} u_{n-1} du_{n-1} \dots du_1 = \int_0^x \dots \int_0^{u_{n-3}} \frac{u_{n-2}^2}{2} du_{n-2} \dots du_1$$

$$C_n = \int_0^x \dots \int_0^{u_{n-3}} \frac{u_{n-3}^3}{2 \cdot 3} du_{n-3} \dots du_1 = \int_0^x \dots \int_0^{u_{n-4}} \frac{u_{n-4}^4}{2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4} du_{n-4} \dots du_1$$

$$C_n = \dots = \int_0^x \frac{u_1^{n-1}}{2 \cdot 3 \dots (n-1)} du_1 = \frac{x^n}{2 \cdot 3 \dots (n-1) \cdot n} = \frac{x^n}{n!}$$

Then:

$$\hat{T}(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \hat{d}^n \frac{x^n}{n!}$$

In other words, the translation operator is explicitly given by:

$$\hat{T}(x) = \exp(x\hat{d})$$

3.4.3. Commutation Rules between the Translation Generator and the Position Operator

The essence of first quantization lies in the correspondence between commutators and Poisson brackets. Therefore, in this section we shall obtain the main commutation results between position observables and the translation generator.

Let us take the commutator:

$$\begin{aligned}
[\hat{X}, \hat{T}(x_0)]|x\rangle &= (\hat{X}\hat{T}(x_0) - \hat{T}(x_0)\hat{X})|x\rangle = \hat{X}|x + x_0\rangle - \hat{T}(x_0)x|x\rangle \\
&\Rightarrow [\hat{X}, \hat{T}(x_0)]|x\rangle = (x + x_0)|x + x_0\rangle - x|x + x_0\rangle \\
&\Rightarrow [\hat{X}, \hat{T}(x_0)]|x\rangle = x_0|x + x_0\rangle = x_0\hat{T}(x_0)|x\rangle \quad \forall |x\rangle \\
&\Rightarrow [\hat{X}, \hat{T}(x_0)] = x_0\hat{T}(x_0)
\end{aligned}$$

By substituting the previously obtained expression, one has:

$$\begin{aligned}
\left[\hat{X}, \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\hat{d}^n x_0^n}{n!} \right] &= x_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\hat{d}^n x_0^n}{n!} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\hat{d}^n x_0^{n+1}}{n!} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\hat{d}^{n-1} x_0^n}{(n-1)!} \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{[\hat{X}, \hat{d}^n] x_0^n}{n!} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\hat{d}^{n-1} x_0^n}{(n-1)!}
\end{aligned}$$

As for $n = 0$ we have $[\hat{X}, I] = 0$, it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{[\hat{X}, \hat{d}^n] x_0^n}{n!} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{n\hat{d}^{n-1} x_0^n}{n!} \\
\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{([\hat{X}, \hat{d}^n] - n\hat{d}^{n-1}) x_0^n}{n!} &= 0 \quad \forall x_0
\end{aligned}$$

Since \hat{X} and \hat{d} are independent of x_0 , and the powers x_0^n are linearly independent, a fundamental commutation rule is obtained:

$$[\hat{X}, \hat{d}^n] = n\hat{d}^{n-1} \quad \forall n \geq 1$$

From which it follows that for $n = 1$ the fundamental commutation relation is:

$$[\hat{X}, \hat{d}] = I$$

Thus, we take:

$$[\hat{X}^2, \hat{d}] = \hat{X}[\hat{X}, \hat{d}] + [\hat{X}, \hat{d}]\hat{X} = \hat{X} + \hat{X} = 2\hat{X}$$

$$[\hat{X}^3, \hat{d}] = \hat{X}[\hat{X}^2, \hat{d}] + [\hat{X}, \hat{d}]\hat{X}^2 = \hat{X}2\hat{X} + \hat{X}^2 = 3\hat{X}^2$$

Assuming the hypothesis $[\hat{X}^n, \hat{d}] = n\hat{X}^{n-1}$, we then have:

$$[\hat{X}^{n+1}, \hat{d}] = \hat{X}[\hat{X}^n, \hat{d}] + [\hat{X}, \hat{d}]\hat{X}^n = \hat{X}n\hat{X}^{n-1} + \hat{X}^n = (n+1)\hat{X}^n$$

Thus, the hypothesis is demonstrated, namely:

$$[\hat{X}^n, \hat{d}] = n\hat{X}^{n-1} \quad \forall n \geq 1$$

Now, let us look at the expectation value of the position after a translation:

$$\langle \hat{X} \rangle_T = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^\dagger \hat{X} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{X} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle$$

Since $[\hat{X}, \hat{T}] = x_0 \hat{T}$ then $\hat{X} \hat{T} = \hat{T} \hat{X} + x_0 \hat{T}$, replacing:

$$\langle \hat{X} \rangle_T = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{T} \hat{X} | \psi \rangle + x_0 \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle$$

$$\langle \hat{X} \rangle_T = \langle \psi | \hat{X} | \psi \rangle + x_0 \langle \psi | \psi \rangle \Rightarrow \langle \hat{X} \rangle_T = \langle \hat{X} \rangle + x_0$$

In other words, the expectation value of the position is displaced by exactly the same amount as that introduced by the translation operator.

To study the generator \hat{d} , we must turn it into an *observable*. Since it is anti-Hermitian, we redefine it as $\hat{D} = i\hat{d}$, which can be readily verified to be Hermitian. With this, the translation operator and the commutation relations become:

$$\hat{T}(x_0) = \exp(-x_0 i \hat{D})$$

$$[\hat{X}, \hat{D}^n] = in \hat{D}^{n-1}$$

$$[\hat{X}^n, \hat{D}] = in \hat{X}^{n-1}$$

$$[\hat{X}, \hat{D}] = iI$$

$$\hat{D}|x\rangle = i \frac{\partial}{\partial x} |x\rangle \tag{7}$$

With this, the expectation value of this hypothetical observable is:

$$\langle \hat{D} \rangle_T = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^\dagger \hat{D} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{D} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle$$

Since \hat{T} contains only powers of \hat{D} , the two commute, thus:

$$\langle \hat{D} \rangle_T = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{T} \hat{D} | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | \hat{D} | \psi \rangle$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle \hat{D} \rangle_T = \langle \hat{D} \rangle_i$$

This shows that the observable \hat{D} is preserved under translations.

3.4.4. Generalization to the Case of N Degrees of Freedom

In the general case, we take the Kronecker product of several translation operators as follows:

$$\hat{T} = \hat{T}_1 \otimes \hat{T}_2 \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_N = \prod_{j=1}^N \hat{T}_j$$

Where each $\hat{T}_j = \hat{T}_j(x_{0j})$ is a one-dimensional operator in the j -th degree of freedom, which is well defined as we have seen above.

Let us apply this operator to the *ket* $|\vec{r}\rangle$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}|\vec{r}\rangle &= (\hat{T}_1 \otimes \hat{T}_2 \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_N)(|x_1\rangle \otimes |x_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_N\rangle) \\ \hat{T}|\vec{r}\rangle &= \hat{T}_1|x_1\rangle \otimes \hat{T}_2|x_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_N|x_N\rangle \\ \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0)|\vec{r}\rangle &= |x_1 + x_{01}\rangle \otimes |x_2 + x_{02}\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_N + x_{0N}\rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0)|\vec{r}\rangle = |\vec{r} + \vec{r}_0\rangle$$

We see that its translation results in a net translation of \vec{r}_0 in phase space.

Let us verify the fulfillment of Properties 6 through 9:

Prop 6: $\hat{T}(0)|\vec{r}\rangle = |\vec{r} + 0\rangle = |\vec{r}\rangle \Rightarrow \hat{T}(0) = I$ satisfies

Prop 7: $\hat{T}(\vec{r}_0)\hat{T}(\vec{r}'_0)|\vec{r}\rangle = \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0)|\vec{r} + \vec{r}'_0\rangle = |\vec{r} + \vec{r}_0 + \vec{r}'_0\rangle = \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0 + \vec{r}'_0)|\vec{r}\rangle$

$\Rightarrow \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0)\hat{T}(\vec{r}'_0) = \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0 + \vec{r}'_0)$ which holds together with the symmetry property

Prop 8: $\hat{T}(\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_0) = \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0)\hat{T}(-\vec{r}_0) = \hat{T}(-\vec{r}_0)\hat{T}(\vec{r}_0) = \hat{T}(0) = I \Rightarrow \hat{T}^{-1}(\vec{r}_0) = \hat{T}(-\vec{r}_0)$ satisfies

Prop 9: $\hat{T}^\dagger = \left(\prod_{j=1}^N \hat{T}_j\right)^\dagger = \prod_{j=1}^N \hat{T}_j^\dagger = \prod_{j=1}^N \hat{T}_j(-x_{0j}) = \hat{T}(-\vec{r}_0) = \hat{T}^{-1}$ satisfies

Now let us study the commutators:

$$[\hat{R}, \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0)] = \hat{R}\hat{T} - \hat{T}\hat{R}$$

Where it is understood $\hat{T} = \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0)$.

Let us inspect each term:

$$\hat{R}\hat{T} = (\hat{X}_1^*, \hat{X}_2^*, \dots, \hat{X}_N^*)\hat{T} = (\hat{X}_1^*\hat{T}, \hat{X}_2^*\hat{T}, \dots, \hat{X}_N^*\hat{T})$$

$$\hat{T}\hat{R} = \hat{T}(\hat{X}_1^*, \hat{X}_2^*, \dots, \hat{X}_N^*) = (\hat{T}\hat{X}_1^*, \hat{T}\hat{X}_2^*, \dots, \hat{T}\hat{X}_N^*)$$

Then

$$[\hat{R}, \hat{T}] = ([\hat{X}_1^*, \hat{T}], [\hat{X}_2^*, \hat{T}], \dots, [\hat{X}_N^*, \hat{T}])$$

Since

$$\hat{X}_j^* \hat{T} = (I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I)(\hat{T}_1 \otimes \hat{T}_2 \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_N) = \hat{T}_1 \otimes \hat{T}_2 \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \hat{T}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_N$$

$$\hat{T} \hat{X}_j^* = (\hat{T}_1 \otimes \hat{T}_2 \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_N)(I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I) = \hat{T}_1 \otimes \hat{T}_2 \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_j \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_N$$

then

$$[\hat{X}_j^*, \hat{T}] = \hat{T}_1 \otimes \hat{T}_2 \cdots \otimes [\hat{X}_j, \hat{T}_j] \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_N = x_{0j} \hat{T}$$

Thus it becomes:

$$[\hat{R}, \hat{T}] = (x_{01} \hat{T}, x_{02} \hat{T}, \dots, x_{0N} \hat{T}) \Rightarrow [\hat{R}, \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0)] = \vec{r}_0 \hat{T}(\vec{r}_0) \quad (8)$$

Since the generators \hat{D}_j are observables, we then define their version for N dimensions analogously to the position, as follows:

$$\hat{\Omega} = (\hat{D}_1^*, \hat{D}_2^*, \dots, \hat{D}_N^*)$$

Where

$$\hat{D}_j^* = I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I$$

Which analogously gives us

$$\hat{D}_j^* |\vec{r}\rangle = |x_1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_j |x_j\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_N\rangle = |x_1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes i \frac{\partial |x_j\rangle}{\partial x_j} \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_N\rangle$$

$$\hat{D}_j^* |\vec{r}\rangle = i \frac{\partial |\vec{r}\rangle}{\partial x_j}$$

We now examine whether \hat{T} and $\hat{\Omega}$ commute, in analogy with the one-dimensional case.

$$\hat{\Omega} \hat{T} = (\hat{D}_1^*, \hat{D}_2^*, \dots, \hat{D}_N^*) \hat{T} = (\hat{D}_1^* \hat{T}, \hat{D}_2^* \hat{T}, \dots, \hat{D}_N^* \hat{T})$$

$$\text{Since } \hat{D}_j^* \hat{T} = (I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I)(\hat{T}_1 \otimes \hat{T}_2 \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_N) = \hat{T}_1 \otimes \hat{T}_2 \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_j \hat{T}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{T}_N$$

And knowing that in the one-dimensional case \hat{D}_j and \hat{T}_j commute, then

$$\hat{D}_j^* \hat{T} = \hat{T} \hat{D}_j^*$$

Therefore:

$$\hat{\Omega} \hat{T} = (\hat{T} \hat{D}_1^*, \hat{T} \hat{D}_2^*, \dots, \hat{T} \hat{D}_N^*) = \hat{T} \hat{\Omega}$$

Regarding the position operators, we have:

$$[\hat{X}_i^*, \hat{X}_j^*] |\vec{r}\rangle = x_j x_i |\vec{r}\rangle - x_i x_j |\vec{r}\rangle = 0 \Rightarrow [\hat{X}_i^*, \hat{X}_j^*] = 0$$

And for the case of the observables \hat{D}_j^* , we obtain:

$$[\hat{D}_i^*, \hat{D}_j^*]|\vec{r}\rangle = i^2 \frac{\partial^2 |\vec{r}\rangle}{\partial x_j \partial x_i} - i^2 \frac{\partial^2 |\vec{r}\rangle}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} = 0 \Rightarrow [\hat{D}_i^*, \hat{D}_j^*] = 0$$

The commutator between the two observables is:

$$[\hat{X}_j^*, \hat{D}_l^*] = \hat{X}_j^* \hat{D}_l^* - \hat{D}_l^* \hat{X}_j^*$$

If $j \neq l$

$$\hat{X}_j^* \hat{D}_l^* = (I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I)(I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_l \otimes \cdots \otimes I) = I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_l \otimes \cdots \otimes I$$

$$\hat{D}_l^* \hat{X}_j^* = (I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_l \otimes \cdots \otimes I)(I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I) = I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_l \otimes \cdots \otimes I$$

$$\Rightarrow [\hat{X}_j^*, \hat{D}_l^*] = 0$$

If $j = l$

$$\hat{X}_j^* \hat{D}_j^* = (I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I)(I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I) = I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \hat{D}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I$$

$$\hat{D}_j^* \hat{X}_j^* = (I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I)(I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I) = I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{D}_j \hat{X}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I$$

$$[\hat{X}_j^*, \hat{D}_j^*] = I \otimes \cdots \otimes [\hat{X}_j, \hat{D}_j] \otimes \cdots \otimes I = I \otimes \cdots \otimes iI_{\text{pos } j} \otimes \cdots \otimes I = iI_N$$

$$\Rightarrow [\hat{X}_j^*, \hat{D}_j^*] = i\delta_{jl}$$

3.5. Construction of the canonical momentum operator

To postulate the canonical momentum, we will first study the expectation values of \hat{R} and the observable $\hat{\Omega}$ under a translation transformation:

$$\langle \hat{R} \rangle_T = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^\dagger \hat{R} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{R} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle$$

Since $[\hat{R}, \hat{T}] = \vec{r}_0 \hat{T}$ then $\hat{R} \hat{T} = \hat{T} \hat{R} + \vec{r}_0 \hat{T}$, replacing:

$$\langle \hat{R} \rangle_T = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{T} \hat{R} | \psi \rangle + \vec{r}_0 \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle$$

$$\langle \hat{R} \rangle_T = \langle \psi | \hat{R} | \psi \rangle + \vec{r}_0 \langle \psi | \psi \rangle$$

$$\langle \hat{R} \rangle_T = \langle \hat{R} \rangle_i + \vec{r}_0$$

Furthermore, the expectation value of the observable $\hat{\Omega}$ can be expressed as:

$$\langle \hat{\Omega} \rangle_T = \langle \psi | \hat{T} | \hat{\Omega} | \hat{T} \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^\dagger \hat{\Omega} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{\Omega} \hat{T} | \psi \rangle$$

Since $\hat{\Omega} \hat{T} = \hat{T} \hat{\Omega}$ then:

$$\langle \hat{\Omega} \rangle_T = \langle \psi | \hat{T}^{-1} \hat{T} \hat{\Omega} | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | \hat{\Omega} | \psi \rangle$$

$$\langle \hat{\Omega} \rangle_T = \langle \hat{\Omega} \rangle_i$$

This means that if we shift the coordinate system by a fixed amount, the expected value of the system's position is effectively shifted by the same amount, but the observable $\hat{\Omega}$ remains invariant under these translations. This reminds us of a well-known result of theoretical mechanics in which a translational change of coordinates leaves the canonical momenta of the system invariant.

Therefore, $\hat{\Omega}$ must be the observable of canonical momentum, and thus we will naturally say:

$$\hat{\Pi} = \epsilon \hat{\Omega} = (\hat{P}_1^*, \hat{P}_2^*, \dots, \hat{P}_N^*)$$

With

$$\hat{P}_j^* = I \otimes \dots \otimes \hat{P}_j \otimes \dots \otimes I$$

With this, the commutation relations and the translation operators are:

$$[\hat{X}_j^*, \hat{X}_l^*] = 0 ; \quad [\hat{P}_j^*, \hat{P}_l^*] = 0 ; \quad [\hat{X}_j^*, \hat{P}_l^*] = i\epsilon \delta_{jl} ; \quad \hat{T}_j(x_{0j}) = \exp\left(-i \frac{x_{0j}}{\epsilon} \hat{P}_j\right) \quad (9)$$

And in the one-dimensional case we have:

$$[\hat{X}, \hat{P}] = i\epsilon ; \quad [\hat{X}, \hat{P}^n] = i\epsilon n \hat{P}^{n-1} ; \quad [\hat{X}^n, \hat{P}] = i\epsilon n \hat{X}^{n-1} ; \quad \hat{T}(x_0) = \exp\left(-i \frac{x_0}{\epsilon} \hat{P}\right) \quad (10)$$

Up to this point we have partially constructed Postulate VI of quantum mechanics. It will be when ϵ is postulated as the reduced Planck constant that we will have this postulate fully established.

The important aspect so far lies in the natural emergence of the canonical momentum operator as the generator of the translation operator, without the need to previously know Schrödinger's equation, since we started from the first four axiomatic postulates and a purely abstract algebra in the Hilbert space of quantum states.

In the next unit, we begin the path toward Schrödinger's equation, which will seek to find the generator of time evolution and the representation of this entire algebra in terms of differential operators and scalars on wave functions.

3.6. Expectation values of macroscopic observables

The correspondence principle, stated by Niels Bohr, dictates that at the macroscopic scale quantum mechanics must reproduce theoretical mechanics; therefore, in the construction of this theory, the expectation values must be related to the canonical functions of the system. Thus, we will begin by studying the expectation values of observables for which their dispersion $\Delta\hat{A}$ is negligible, that is, we will strategically study systems with $\Delta A = 0$.

Let \hat{A} be an observable, it is defined

$$\Delta\hat{A} = \hat{A} - \langle\hat{A}\rangle I$$

then:

$$\Delta\hat{A}^\dagger = \hat{A}^\dagger - \langle\hat{A}\rangle I = \hat{A} - \langle\hat{A}\rangle I = \Delta\hat{A}$$

In other words, $\Delta\hat{A}$ is Hermitian, and therefore

$$\Delta A = \sqrt{\langle(\hat{A} - \langle\hat{A}\rangle I)^2\rangle} = \sqrt{\langle\Delta\hat{A}^2\rangle}.$$

Now, considering the condition $\Delta A = 0$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle\Delta\hat{A}^2\rangle = 0 &\Rightarrow \langle\psi|\Delta\hat{A}^2|\psi\rangle = 0 \Rightarrow \langle\psi\Delta\hat{A}^\dagger|\Delta\hat{A}\psi\rangle = \langle\psi\Delta\hat{A}|\Delta\hat{A}\psi\rangle = 0 \\ &\Rightarrow \|\Delta\hat{A}\psi\| = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Let \hat{Q} be another observable, let us take the expectation value

$$\langle\Delta\hat{A}\hat{Q}\rangle = \langle\psi|\Delta\hat{A}\hat{Q}|\psi\rangle = \langle\psi\Delta\hat{A}|\hat{Q}\psi\rangle,$$

then, by the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality:

$$|\langle\psi\Delta\hat{A}|\hat{Q}\psi\rangle| \leq \|\Delta\hat{A}\psi\| \|\hat{Q}\psi\| = 0 \Rightarrow \langle\Delta\hat{A}\hat{Q}\rangle = 0$$

Then:

$$\langle\Delta A\hat{Q}\rangle = \langle(\hat{A} - \langle\hat{A}\rangle I)\hat{Q}\rangle = \langle\hat{A}\hat{Q}\rangle - \langle\hat{A}\rangle\langle\hat{Q}\rangle \Rightarrow \langle\hat{A}\hat{Q}\rangle = \langle\hat{A}\rangle\langle\hat{Q}\rangle$$

Note that this property does not require $\Delta Q = 0$, but rather tells us that it is enough for one observable to have zero uncertainty for the expectation value to be distributive between both.

Let us consider a generalization of this property:

$$\langle\hat{A}^2\hat{Q}\rangle = \langle\hat{A}\rangle\langle\hat{A}\hat{Q}\rangle = \langle\hat{A}\rangle^2\langle\hat{Q}\rangle$$

Let the hypothesis be

$$\langle\hat{A}^n\hat{Q}\rangle = \langle\hat{A}\rangle^n\langle\hat{Q}\rangle$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle\hat{A}^{n+1}\hat{Q}\rangle = \langle\hat{A}(\hat{A}^n\hat{Q})\rangle = \langle\hat{A}\rangle\langle\hat{A}^n\hat{Q}\rangle = \langle\hat{A}\rangle\langle\hat{A}\rangle^n\langle\hat{Q}\rangle = \langle\hat{A}\rangle^{n+1}\langle\hat{Q}\rangle$$

In particular, if we set $\hat{Q} = I$, then:

$$\langle \hat{A}^n \rangle = \langle \hat{A} \rangle^n \cdot 1 = \langle \hat{A} \rangle^n \Rightarrow \langle \hat{A}^n \rangle = \langle \hat{A} \rangle^n$$

Thus, given two observables \hat{A}_1 and \hat{A}_2 satisfying $\Delta A_1 = 0$ and $\Delta A_2 = 0$, it follows that:

$$\langle \hat{A}_1^{m_1} \hat{A}_2^{m_2} \rangle = \langle \hat{A}_1^{m_1} \rangle \langle \hat{A}_2^{m_2} \rangle = \langle \hat{A}_1 \rangle^{m_1} \langle \hat{A}_2 \rangle^{m_2}$$

This result can be readily generalized to:

$$\left\langle \prod_{k=1}^n \hat{A}_k^{m_k} \right\rangle = \prod_{k=1}^n \langle \hat{A}_k \rangle^{m_k} \quad / \quad \Delta A_k = 0$$

Let \hat{M} be a monomial of position observables $\hat{X}_1^* \hat{X}_2^* \dots, \hat{X}_N^*$ and canonical momenta $\hat{P}_1^* \hat{P}_2^* \dots, \hat{P}_N^*$, then:

$$\langle \hat{M}((\dots \hat{X}_k^* \dots), (\dots \hat{P}_k^* \dots)) \rangle = M((\dots \langle \hat{X}_k^* \rangle \dots), (\dots \langle \hat{P}_k^* \rangle \dots))$$

Even better, if a function F of the aforementioned observables admits a power series expansion, then it is an expansion in monomials of the form of \hat{M} , then:

$$\langle \hat{F}((\dots \hat{X}_k^* \dots), (\dots \hat{P}_k^* \dots)) \rangle = F((\dots \langle \hat{X}_k^* \rangle \dots), (\dots \langle \hat{P}_k^* \rangle \dots)) \quad (11)$$

Where each $\Delta X_k^* = 0$ y $\Delta P_k^* = 0$.

This result is important because it states that, in the macroscopic case, the expectation value of a function of the position and momentum observables is simply the function evaluated at the expectation values of these.

3.7. Construction of the first quantization

3.7.1. Commutators of functions with power series

At the end of section 3.5 we saw the commutators

$$[\hat{X}, \hat{P}^n] = i\epsilon n \hat{P}^{n-1} \quad \text{y} \quad [\hat{X}^n, \hat{P}] = i\epsilon n \hat{X}^{n-1}$$

which seem to relate the derivative of a power with commutators.

This property will be the starting point for relating the famous *Poisson* brackets with the commutators, which are one of the pillars of first quantization.

Let the polynomial function of observables $f(\hat{A})$ be given by the general series.

$$f(\hat{A}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \hat{A}^n \quad \forall a_n \in \mathbb{C}$$

The derivative is defined as follows:

$$f'(\hat{A}) = \frac{\partial f}{\partial \hat{A}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n a_n \hat{A}^{n-1}$$

Now, we define $f(\hat{A})$ as an Analytic function of operators if it has a Maclaurin series as follow:

$$f(\hat{A}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!} \hat{A}^n$$

Here, $f^{(n)}(0)$ denotes the n -th derivative of the function evaluated at the scalar argument 0. Thus, it follows that the function may likewise be regarded as a polynomial function.

Based on these definitions, we may state the following theorem:

Theorem.

Let $f(\hat{X})$ and $g(\hat{P})$ be functions with Maclaurin series, where \hat{X} and \hat{P} are the one-dimensional position and momentum operators respectively, then:

$$If [\hat{X}, \hat{P}] = i\epsilon \quad \Rightarrow \quad [f(\hat{X}), g(\hat{P})] = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} f^{(k)}(\hat{X}) g^{(k)}(\hat{P})$$

The proof of this theorem is shown in Annex 6.2.

From the theorem we retain only first-order terms, with which we obtain:

$$[f(\hat{X}), g(\hat{P})] \approx i\epsilon f^{(1)}(\hat{X}) g^{(1)}(\hat{P}) = i\epsilon \frac{\partial f}{\partial \hat{X}} \frac{\partial g}{\partial \hat{P}}$$

Let us now consider the commutator of the form $[f_1(\hat{X})f_2(\hat{P}), g_1(\hat{X})g_2(\hat{P})]$:

$$[f_1(\hat{X})f_2(\hat{P}), g_1(\hat{X})g_2(\hat{P})] = [f_1f_2, g_1g_2] = f_1[f_2, g_1g_2] + [f_1, g_1g_2]f_2$$

$$[f_1f_2, g_1g_2] = f_1 \left(g_1 \underbrace{[f_2, g_2]}_0 + [f_2, g_1]g_2 \right) + \left(g_1[f_1, g_2] + \underbrace{[f_1, g_1]}_0 g_2 \right) f_2$$

$$[f_1f_2, g_1g_2] = f_1[f_2, g_1]g_2 + g_1[f_1, g_2]f_2 = -i\epsilon f_1 \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial \hat{X}} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \hat{P}} g_2 + i\epsilon \underbrace{g_1 \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \hat{X}}}_{\text{Commut}} \underbrace{\frac{\partial g_2}{\partial \hat{P}} f_2}_{\text{Commut}}$$

$$[f_1f_2, g_1g_2] = i\epsilon \left(\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \hat{X}} g_1 f_2 \frac{\partial g_2}{\partial \hat{P}} - f_1 \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial \hat{X}} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \hat{P}} g_2 \right)$$

Considering the commutators:

$$[g_1, f_2] = g_1f_2 - f_2g_1 = i\epsilon \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial \hat{X}} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \hat{P}} \quad \Rightarrow \quad g_1f_2 = f_2g_1 + i\epsilon \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial \hat{X}} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \hat{P}}$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial g_1}{\partial \hat{X}}, \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \hat{P}} \right] = \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial \hat{X}} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \hat{P}} - \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \hat{P}} \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial \hat{X}} = i\epsilon \frac{\partial^2 g_1}{\partial \hat{X}^2} \frac{\partial^2 f_2}{\partial \hat{P}^2} \Rightarrow \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial \hat{X}} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \hat{P}} = \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \hat{P}} \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial \hat{X}} + i\epsilon \frac{\partial^2 g_1}{\partial \hat{X}^2} \frac{\partial^2 f_2}{\partial \hat{P}^2}$$

We see that changing the order of the product implies adding a term proportional to $i\epsilon$. Since everything is multiplied by ϵ , the extra terms only appear as second-order terms. Moreover, this implies that, to first order, the functions f_1, f_2, g_1, g_2 commute up to their first derivatives. Then, the result can be summarized as:

$$[f_1f_2, g_1g_2] = i\epsilon \left(\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \hat{X}} f_2 g_1 \frac{\partial g_2}{\partial \hat{P}} - f_1 \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \hat{P}} \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial \hat{X}} g_2 \right)$$

Which may equivalently be expressed as:

$$[f_1(\hat{X})f_2(\hat{P}), g_1(\hat{X})g_2(\hat{P})] = i\epsilon \left(\frac{\partial f_1 f_2}{\partial \hat{X}} \frac{\partial g_1 g_2}{\partial \hat{P}} - \frac{\partial f_1 f_2}{\partial \hat{P}} \frac{\partial g_1 g_2}{\partial \hat{X}} \right)$$

3.7.2. Operator form of the Poisson brackets

The Poisson bracket in its operator form, for the one-dimensional case, is given by:

$$\{\hat{A}, \hat{B}\}_c = \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{X}} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}} - \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{P}} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}}$$

Therefore, the final result of the preceding section may be expressed as:

$$[f_1(\hat{X})f_2(\hat{P}), g_1(\hat{X})g_2(\hat{P})] = i\epsilon \{f_1(\hat{X})f_2(\hat{P}), g_1(\hat{X})g_2(\hat{P})\}_c \quad (12)$$

For a system with N degrees of freedom, this bracket is defined as follows:

$$\{\hat{A}, \hat{B}\}_c = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} - \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*}$$

Here, the partial derivatives are taken with respect to polynomial functions of the canonical operators \hat{X}_k^* and \hat{P}_k^* , and are performed in the same manner as illustrated in the one-dimensional case.

Property 11 The Poisson bracket in its operator form is bilinear

Dem:

$$\begin{aligned} \{\hat{A}_1 + \hat{A}_2, \hat{B}\}_c &= \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial(\hat{A}_1 + \hat{A}_2)}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} - \frac{\partial(\hat{A}_1 + \hat{A}_2)}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \right) \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial \hat{A}_1}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} - \frac{\partial \hat{A}_1}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \right) + \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial \hat{A}_2}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} - \frac{\partial \hat{A}_2}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \right) \\ &= \{\hat{A}_1, \hat{B}\}_c + \{\hat{A}_2, \hat{B}\}_c \end{aligned}$$

Analogously, in the second term of the Poisson bracket.

Let \hat{A}, \hat{B} and \hat{C} be three operational functions that commute, and whose first derivatives also commute:

$$\begin{aligned} \{\hat{A}\hat{B}, \hat{C}\}_c &= \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \hat{B} + \hat{A} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \right) \frac{\partial \hat{C}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} - \left(\frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \hat{B} + \hat{A} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \right) \frac{\partial \hat{C}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \\ \{\hat{A}\hat{B}, \hat{C}\}_c &= \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \hat{B} \frac{\partial \hat{C}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} + \sum_{k=1}^N \hat{A} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{C}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} - \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \hat{B} \frac{\partial \hat{C}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} - \sum_{k=1}^N \hat{A} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{C}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \end{aligned}$$

Since they all commute, then:

$$\{\hat{A}\hat{B}, \hat{C}\}_c = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{C}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \hat{B} - \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{C}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \hat{B} + \hat{A} \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{C}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} - \hat{A} \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{C}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*}$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad \{\hat{A}\hat{B}, \hat{C}\}_c = \{\hat{A}, \hat{C}\}_c \hat{B} + \hat{A} \{\hat{B}, \hat{C}\}_c$$

Let us now examine another property:

$$\{\hat{A}, \hat{B}\}_c = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} - \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} = - \left(\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} - \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \right)$$

Since they mutually commute, it follows that:

$$\{\hat{A}, \hat{B}\}_c = - \left(\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} - \frac{\partial \hat{B}}{\partial \hat{P}_k^*} \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial \hat{X}_k^*} \right) \Rightarrow \quad \{\hat{A}, \hat{B}\}_c = -\{\hat{B}, \hat{A}\}_c$$

These properties indicate to us that if the operators involved and their first derivatives commute, then the operational Poisson brackets have the same algebra as the commutators.

3.7.3. Equivalence between commutators and Poisson brackets in the correspondence principle

We will begin by working with monomials. In general, any monomial of powers in \hat{X} and \hat{P} can be represented as:

$$\hat{M} = \prod_{k=1}^n f_k \quad / \quad f_k = \hat{X}^{m_k} \hat{P}^{n_k}$$

Let us see the commutator of two of these *monomials*:

$$\hat{M}_a = \prod_{k=1}^n f_k \quad ; \quad \hat{M}_b = \prod_{k=1}^m g_k$$

$$[\hat{M}_a, \hat{M}_b] = \left[\prod_{k=1}^n f_k, \prod_{k=1}^m g_k \right]$$

Which, by the commutator algebra, takes the form:

$$[\hat{M}_a, \hat{M}_b] = \sum_{j,l \in Q} (\dots [f_j, g_l] \dots)$$

Where Q represents the set of all possible commutation pairs. From the result of Section 3.7.1 we have:

$$[f_j, g_l] \approx i\epsilon \{f_j, g_l\}_c$$

Which, after substitution, we have:

$$[\hat{M}_a, \hat{M}_b] \approx i\epsilon \sum_{j,l \in Q} (\dots \{f_j, g_l\}_c \dots)$$

As indicated in Section 3.7.1, to first order in ϵ the terms f_j and g_l commute up to their first derivatives; therefore, by adding the result of Section 3.7.2, it is concluded that the algebra of the brackets f_j, g_l is the same as that of the commutators, therefore:

$$[\hat{M}_a, \hat{M}_b] \approx i\epsilon \left\{ \prod_{k=1}^n f_k, \prod_{l=1}^m g_l \right\}_c \Rightarrow [\hat{M}_a, \hat{M}_b] \approx i\epsilon \{\hat{M}_a, \hat{M}_b\}_c$$

And more generally, let $\hat{A}(\hat{X}, \hat{P})$ and $\hat{B}(\hat{X}, \hat{P})$ be two operators with power series, that is:

$$\hat{A}(\hat{X}, \hat{P}) = \sum_{\vec{n} \in Q_a} a_{\vec{n}} \hat{M}_{a\vec{n}}, \quad \hat{B}(\hat{X}, \hat{P}) = \sum_{\vec{m} \in Q_b} b_{\vec{m}} \hat{M}_{b\vec{m}}$$

Here, $\hat{M}_{a\vec{n}}$ and $\hat{M}_{b\vec{m}}$ denote monomials of the form specified earlier. Thus:

$$\begin{aligned} [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] &= \left[\sum_{\vec{n} \in Q_a} a_{\vec{n}} \hat{M}_{a\vec{n}}, \sum_{\vec{m} \in Q_b} b_{\vec{m}} \hat{M}_{b\vec{m}} \right] = \sum_{\vec{n} \in Q_a} a_{\vec{n}} \left[\hat{M}_{a\vec{n}}, \sum_{\vec{m} \in Q_b} b_{\vec{m}} \hat{M}_{b\vec{m}} \right] \\ [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] &= \sum_{\vec{n} \in Q_a} \sum_{\vec{m} \in Q_b} a_{\vec{n}} b_{\vec{m}} [\hat{M}_{a\vec{n}}, \hat{M}_{b\vec{m}}] \approx i\epsilon \sum_{\vec{n} \in Q_a} \sum_{\vec{m} \in Q_b} a_{\vec{n}} b_{\vec{m}} \{\hat{M}_{a\vec{n}}, \hat{M}_{b\vec{m}}\}_c \\ [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] &= i\epsilon \left\{ \sum_{\vec{n} \in Q_a} a_{\vec{n}} \hat{M}_{a\vec{n}}, \sum_{\vec{m} \in Q_b} b_{\vec{m}} \hat{M}_{b\vec{m}} \right\}_c \\ &\Rightarrow [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] \approx i\epsilon \{\hat{A}, \hat{B}\}_c \end{aligned}$$

In the case of N degrees of freedom, we must take monomials associated with each degree of freedom as follows:

$$\hat{M}_k = \prod_{j=1}^n f_{jk} \quad / \quad f_{jk} = (\hat{X}_k^*)^{n_{jk}} (\hat{P}_k^*)^{m_{jk}}$$

Now, taking two monomials associated with this degree of freedom, we calculate their commutator:

$$[\hat{M}_{ak}, \hat{M}_{bk}] = \left[\prod_{j=1}^n f_{jk}, \prod_{j=1}^m g_{jk} \right] = \sum_{j,l \in Q} (\dots [f_{jk}, g_{jl}] \dots)$$

Let us examine each commutator:

$$[f_{jk}, g_{jl}] = [(\hat{X}_k^*)^{n_{jk}} (\hat{P}_k^*)^{m_{jk}}, (\hat{X}_k^*)^{n'_{jl}} (\hat{P}_k^*)^{m'_{jl}}]$$

Since:

$$(\hat{X}_k^*)^{n_{jk}} (\hat{P}_k^*)^{m_{jk}} = (I \otimes \dots \otimes I \otimes \hat{X}_k^{n_{jk}} \otimes I \otimes \dots \otimes I) (I \otimes \dots \otimes \hat{P}_k^{m_{jk}} \otimes I \otimes \dots \otimes I) = I \otimes \dots \otimes \hat{X}_k^{n_{jk}} \hat{P}_k^{m_{jk}} \otimes \dots \otimes I$$

And since the same holds for the second term, then:

$$\left[(\hat{X}_k^*)^{n_{jk}} (\hat{P}_k^*)^{m_{jk}}, (\hat{X}_k^*)^{n'_{jl}} (\hat{P}_k^*)^{m'_{jl}} \right] = I \otimes \dots \otimes [\hat{X}_k^{n_{jk}} \hat{P}_k^{m_{jk}}, \hat{X}_k^{n'_{jl}} \hat{P}_k^{m'_{jl}}] \otimes \dots \otimes I$$

$$\left[(\hat{X}_k^*)^{n_{jk}} (\hat{P}_k^*)^{m_{jk}}, (\hat{X}_k^*)^{n'_{jl}} (\hat{P}_k^*)^{m'_{jl}} \right] \approx i\epsilon I \otimes \dots \otimes \{\hat{X}_k^{n_{jk}} \hat{P}_k^{m_{jk}}, \hat{X}_k^{n'_{jl}} \hat{P}_k^{m'_{jl}}\}_c \otimes \dots \otimes I$$

$$[f_{jk}, g_{jl}] \approx i\epsilon \{f_{jk}, g_{jl}\}_c$$

With this we have:

$$[\hat{M}_{ak}, \hat{M}_{bk}] \approx i\epsilon \sum_{j,l \in Q} (\dots \{f_{jk}, g_{jl}\}_c \dots)$$

In the same way as in the previous section, we use the result that the algebra of commutators and Poisson brackets are the same to first order, hence:

$$[\hat{M}_{ak}, \hat{M}_{bk}] \approx i\epsilon \{\hat{M}_{ak}, \hat{M}_{bk}\}_c$$

Let us now consider monomials of the form

$$\hat{M} = \prod_{k=1}^n \hat{M}_k$$

With this we have:

$$[\hat{M}_a, \hat{M}_b] = \left[\prod_{k=1}^n \hat{M}_k^a, \prod_{k=1}^m \hat{M}_k^b \right] = \sum_{j,l \in Q} (\dots [\hat{M}_j^a, \hat{M}_l^b] \dots) \approx i\epsilon \sum_{j,l \in Q} (\dots \{\hat{M}_j^a, \hat{M}_l^b\}_c \dots)$$

Once again, appealing to the equivalence of brackets and commutators to first order:

$$[\hat{M}_a, \hat{M}_b] \approx i\epsilon \{\hat{M}_a, \hat{M}_b\}_c$$

Let us now consider, in full generality, two polynomial functions in N degrees of freedom:

$$\hat{A}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}) = \sum_{\bar{n} \in Q_a} a_{\bar{n}} \hat{M}_{a\bar{n}} \quad y \quad \hat{B}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}) = \sum_{\bar{m} \in Q_b} b_{\bar{m}} \hat{M}_{b\bar{m}}$$

Where $\hat{M}_{a\bar{n}}$ and $\hat{M}_{b\bar{m}}$ are monomials of the form indicated above for N degrees of freedom. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] &= \left[\sum_{\bar{n} \in Q_a} a_{\bar{n}} \hat{M}_{a\bar{n}}, \sum_{\bar{m} \in Q_b} b_{\bar{m}} \hat{M}_{b\bar{m}} \right] = \sum_{\bar{n} \in Q_a} a_{\bar{n}} \left[\hat{M}_{a\bar{n}}, \sum_{\bar{m} \in Q_b} b_{\bar{m}} \hat{M}_{b\bar{m}} \right] \\ [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] &= \sum_{\bar{n} \in Q_a} \sum_{\bar{m} \in Q_b} a_{\bar{n}} b_{\bar{m}} [\hat{M}_{a\bar{n}}, \hat{M}_{b\bar{m}}] \approx i\epsilon \sum_{\bar{n} \in Q_a} \sum_{\bar{m} \in Q_b} a_{\bar{n}} b_{\bar{m}} \{\hat{M}_{a\bar{n}}, \hat{M}_{b\bar{m}}\}_c \\ [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] &= i\epsilon \left\{ \sum_{\bar{n} \in Q_a} a_{\bar{n}} \hat{M}_{a\bar{n}}, \sum_{\bar{m} \in Q_b} b_{\bar{m}} \hat{M}_{b\bar{m}} \right\}_c \end{aligned}$$

$$[\hat{A}, \hat{B}] \approx i\epsilon \{\hat{A}, \hat{B}\}_c \tag{13}$$

It is precisely this general result one of the fundamental pillars of first quantization, which establishes that the Poisson brackets are transformed into the commutator of operators associated with such observables.

4. Construction of the fifth postulate

In this section, all the necessary elements are presented that explain why the Schrödinger equation is as it is; essentially, the fourth postulate is postulated taking into account all the results seen so far in the purely abstract Hilbert space.

4.1. Representation of the position and momentum operators

To begin, we must first obtain a clear representation of the canonical position and momentum operators. For this, let us start with equation (6):

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{R} | \psi \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \langle \vec{r} | \hat{R} | \vec{r}' \rangle \psi(\vec{r}') d^N r'$$

As can be seen in the second term, this expression also shows the spatial representation of the position operator applied to the system's function ψ . Since $\hat{R} | \vec{r}' \rangle = \vec{r}' | \vec{r}' \rangle$ (obtained in Section 3.3), then:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \vec{r} | \hat{R} | \psi \rangle &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \vec{r}' \langle \vec{r} | \vec{r}' \rangle \psi(\vec{r}') d^N r' = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \vec{r}' \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}') \psi(\vec{r}') d^N r' \\ \langle \vec{r} | \hat{R} | \psi \rangle &= \vec{r} \psi(\vec{r}) \end{aligned}$$

Naming its representation as $\hat{\vec{r}}$, then:

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{R} | \psi \rangle = \vec{r} \psi(\vec{r}) = \hat{\vec{r}} \psi(\vec{r})$$

Then the position operator has as its *representation*:

$$\hat{\vec{r}} = \vec{r} I$$

This implies that for each degree of freedom we have:

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{X}_j^* | \psi \rangle = \hat{x}_j \psi \quad / \quad \hat{x}_j = x_j I \quad (14)$$

For the case of momentum, since we do not have a prior global result, we then work directly with each component:

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \psi \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \vec{r}' \rangle \psi(\vec{r}') d^N r'$$

Since

$$\hat{P}_j^* | \vec{r}' \rangle = (I \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{P}_j \otimes \cdots \otimes I) (|x'_1\rangle \otimes |x'_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x'_N\rangle) = |x'_1\rangle \otimes |x'_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{P}_j |x'_j\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x'_N\rangle$$

$$\rightarrow \langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \vec{r}' \rangle = (\langle x_1 | \otimes \langle x_2 | \otimes \cdots \otimes \langle x_N |) (|x'_1\rangle \otimes |x'_2\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes \hat{P}_j |x'_j\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x'_N\rangle)$$

$$\rightarrow \langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \vec{r}' \rangle = \langle x_1 | x'_1 \rangle \langle x_2 | x'_2 \rangle \cdots \langle x_{j-1} | x'_{j-1} \rangle \langle x_j | \hat{P}_j | x'_j \rangle \langle x_{j+1} | x'_{j+1} \rangle \cdots \langle x_N | x'_N \rangle$$

$$\rightarrow \langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \vec{r}' \rangle = \delta(x_1 - x'_1) \dots \delta(x_{j-1} - x'_{j-1}) \langle x_j | \hat{P}_j | x'_j \rangle \delta(x_{j+1} - x'_{j+1}) \dots \delta(x_N - x'_N)$$

As was seen in the origin of the momentum operator as the generator of translations, it had been obtained that (equation 7):

$$\hat{P}_j | x'_j \rangle = i\epsilon \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_j} | x'_j \rangle \quad \Rightarrow \quad \langle x_j | \hat{P}_j | x'_j \rangle = i\epsilon \langle x_j | \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_j} | x'_j \rangle = i\epsilon \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_j} \langle x_j | x'_j \rangle$$

$$\langle x_j | \hat{P}_j | x'_j \rangle = i\epsilon \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_j} \delta(x_j - x'_j)$$

$$\rightarrow \langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \vec{r}' \rangle = i\epsilon \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_j} [\delta(x_1 - x'_1) \delta(x_2 - x'_2) \dots \delta(x_N - x'_N)]$$

$$\rightarrow \langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \vec{r}' \rangle = i\epsilon \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_j} \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}')$$

Consequently, we obtain:

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \psi \rangle = i\epsilon \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_j} [\delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}')] \psi(\vec{r}') d^N \vec{r}'$$

By the property of the derivatives of a Dirac delta:

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \psi \rangle = -i\epsilon \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}') \frac{\partial \psi(\vec{r}')}{\partial x'_j} d^N \vec{r}'$$

$$\rightarrow \langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \psi \rangle = -i\epsilon \frac{\partial \psi(\vec{r})}{\partial x_j}$$

Then the representation of each momentum operator on the system's function is:

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{P}_j^* | \psi \rangle = \hat{p}_j \psi \quad / \quad \hat{p}_j = -i\epsilon \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \quad (15)$$

Now let us see its generalization to power series. Let \hat{q}_j be any of the operators \hat{x}_j or \hat{p}_j , and consider the case of \hat{q}_j^2 :

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{Q}_j^2 | \psi \rangle = \langle \vec{r} | \hat{Q}_j \hat{Q}_j | \psi \rangle$$

Normalizing $|\hat{Q}_j \psi\rangle$ with its norm $\lambda = |\hat{Q}_j \psi|$, we have

$$|\psi'\rangle = \frac{|\hat{Q}_j \psi\rangle}{\lambda} \quad \text{y} \quad \psi' = \langle \vec{r} | \psi' \rangle,$$

then:

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{Q}_j^2 | \psi \rangle = \lambda \langle \vec{r} | \hat{Q}_j \psi' \rangle = \lambda \hat{q}_j \psi' = \lambda \hat{q}_j \frac{1}{\lambda} \langle \vec{r} | \hat{Q}_j | \psi \rangle = \hat{q}_j \langle \vec{r} | \hat{Q}_j | \psi \rangle = \hat{q}_j^2 \psi$$

Generalizing, let the hypothesis test be $\langle \vec{r} | \hat{Q}_j^n | \psi \rangle = \hat{q}_j^n \psi$, then:

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{Q}_j^{n+1} | \psi \rangle = \langle \vec{r} | \hat{Q}_j \hat{Q}_j^n | \psi \rangle$$

Normalizing $|\hat{Q}_j^n \psi\rangle$ with its norm $\lambda = \|\hat{Q}_j^n \psi\|$, we get

$$|\psi'\rangle = \frac{|\hat{Q}_j^n \psi\rangle}{\lambda}, \quad \psi' = \langle \vec{r}' | \psi' \rangle,$$

then:

$$\langle \vec{r}' | \hat{Q}_j^{n+1} | \psi \rangle = \lambda \langle \vec{r}' | \hat{Q}_j | \psi' \rangle = \lambda \hat{q}_j \psi' = \lambda \hat{q}_j \frac{1}{\lambda} \langle \vec{r}' | \hat{Q}_j^n | \psi \rangle = \hat{q}_j^{n+1} \psi$$

From which it is concluded that:

$$\langle \vec{r}' | (\hat{X}_j^*)^n | \psi \rangle = \hat{x}_j^n \psi, \quad \langle \vec{r}' | (\hat{P}_j^*)^n | \psi \rangle = \hat{p}_j^n \psi, \quad \langle \vec{r}' | (\hat{X}_j^*)^n (\hat{P}_k^*)^m | \psi \rangle = \hat{x}_j^n \hat{p}_k^m \psi$$

The last rule shows that any monomial with powers of momenta and position operators of multiple degrees of freedom, combined in any order, has the same representation in phase space; that is:

$$\langle \vec{r}' | \hat{M}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}) | \psi \rangle = \hat{M}(\hat{r}, \hat{p}) \psi$$

If $\hat{F}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi})$ is a polynomial function or admits a power series expansion of an arbitrary function, then:

$$\hat{F}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}) = \sum_{\vec{n} \in Q} b_{\vec{n}} \hat{M}_{\vec{n}}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi})$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle \vec{r}' | \hat{F}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}) | \psi \rangle = \sum_{\vec{n} \in Q} b_{\vec{n}} \langle \vec{r}' | \hat{M}_{\vec{n}}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}) | \psi \rangle = \sum_{\vec{n} \in Q} b_{\vec{n}} M_{\vec{n}}(\hat{r}, \hat{p}) \psi = \left(\sum_{\vec{n} \in Q} b_{\vec{n}} M_{\vec{n}}(\hat{r}, \hat{p}) \right) \psi$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle \vec{r}' | \hat{F}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}) | \psi \rangle = F(\hat{r}, \hat{p}) \psi \quad (16)$$

Now, the expectation values of the observables are calculated as follows:

$$\langle \psi | \hat{X}_j^* | \psi \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \langle \psi | \hat{X}_j^* | \vec{r}' \rangle \langle \vec{r}' | \psi \rangle d^N \vec{r}' = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \psi^\dagger(\vec{r}') \hat{x}_j \psi(\vec{r}') d^N \vec{r}'$$

Analogously, for the canonical momentum:

$$\langle \psi | \hat{P}_j^* | \psi \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \psi^\dagger(\vec{r}') \hat{p}_j \psi(\vec{r}') d^N \vec{r}'$$

If we take a monomial of the form $(\hat{X}_j^*)^n (\hat{P}_k^*)^m$, then its expectation value is:

$$\langle \psi | (\hat{X}_j^*)^n (\hat{P}_k^*)^m | \psi \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \langle \psi | (\hat{X}_j^*)^n (\hat{P}_k^*)^m | \vec{r}' \rangle \langle \vec{r}' | \psi \rangle d^N \vec{r}'$$

Since $\langle \vec{r}' | (\hat{X}_j^*)^n (\hat{P}_k^*)^m | \psi \rangle = \hat{x}_j^n \hat{p}_k^m \psi \Rightarrow \langle \psi | (\hat{X}_j^*)^n (\hat{P}_k^*)^m | \vec{r}' \rangle = \psi^\dagger(\vec{r}') \hat{x}_j^n \hat{p}_k^m$, then:

$$\langle \vec{r}' | (\hat{X}_j^*)^n (\hat{P}_k^*)^m | \psi \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \psi^\dagger(\vec{r}') \hat{x}_j^n \hat{p}_k^m \psi(\vec{r}') d^N \vec{r}'$$

We see that it can be easily generalized to the case of any function with a Maclaurin power series.

$$\langle \psi | \hat{F}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}) | \psi \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \psi^\dagger(\vec{r}') \hat{F}(\hat{r}, \hat{p}) \psi(\vec{r}') d^N \vec{r}'$$

$$\langle \hat{F}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}) \rangle_\alpha = \langle \hat{F}(\hat{r}, \hat{p}) \rangle \quad / \quad \langle \dots \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \psi^\dagger(\vec{r}') (\dots) \psi(\vec{r}') d^N \vec{r}'$$

That is, the expectation value is performed by an integration over phase space.

4.2. Deduction of the Schrödinger equation

We have seen that the evolution of the expectation value of an observable \hat{A} is given by equation (03):

$$\frac{d\langle \hat{A} \rangle}{dt} = \langle [\hat{A}, \hat{G}] \rangle + \left\langle \frac{\partial \hat{A}}{\partial t} \right\rangle$$

And according to equation (11) for macroscopic values (where $\epsilon \approx 0$), we have:

$$\langle \hat{A}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}) \rangle = A(\langle \hat{R} \rangle, \langle \hat{\Pi} \rangle) = A(\langle \hat{r} \rangle, \langle \hat{p} \rangle)$$

In which, in the last equality, we have represented the expectation value of the observables in phase space. Renaming the expectation values as $\langle \hat{r} \rangle = \vec{r}$ and $\langle \hat{p} \rangle = \vec{p}$, and A as the system function (it can be an angular momentum or energy of the system, etc.), then:

$$\frac{d\langle \hat{A} \rangle}{dt} = \frac{dA(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)}{dt}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial \hat{A}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}, t)}{\partial t} \right\rangle &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \hat{A}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}, t) \rangle = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} A(\langle \hat{r} \rangle, \langle \hat{p} \rangle, t) \\ &\Rightarrow \frac{\partial \langle \hat{A} \rangle}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial A(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)}{\partial t} \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, according to the correspondence principle, it was found that first quantization achieves an equivalence between Poisson brackets and commutators; this is accomplished by starting from equation (13) and applying it to the commutator with the time evolution generator \hat{G} :

$$\langle [\hat{A}, \hat{G}] \rangle \approx i\epsilon \langle \{ \hat{A}, \hat{G} \}_c \rangle = i\epsilon \langle \{ \hat{A}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}, t), \hat{G}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}, t) \}_c \rangle$$

Using equation (11) again:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle [\hat{A}, \hat{G}] \rangle &\approx i\epsilon \left\{ A(\langle \hat{R} \rangle, \langle \hat{\Pi} \rangle, t), G(\langle \hat{R} \rangle, \langle \hat{\Pi} \rangle, t) \right\} \\ &\Rightarrow \langle [\hat{A}, \hat{G}] \rangle \approx i\epsilon \left\{ A(\langle \hat{r} \rangle, \langle \hat{p} \rangle, t), G(\langle \hat{r} \rangle, \langle \hat{p} \rangle, t) \right\} \\ &\Rightarrow \langle [\hat{A}, \hat{G}] \rangle \approx i\epsilon \left\{ A(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t), G(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Where the subscript “c” has been removed from the brackets, since we are now working with scalar quantities, performing true partial derivatives that are no longer a mere artifact

in the space of abstract operators. With this, the evolution of any system function for macroscopic quantities must be:

$$\frac{dA(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)}{dt} = i\epsilon\{A(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t), G(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)\} + \frac{\partial A(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)}{\partial t}$$

Now we can cite an important result from theoretical mechanics, which tells us that the evolution of any system function is given by:

$$\frac{dA(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)}{dt} = \{A(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t), H(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)\} + \frac{\partial A(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)}{\partial t}$$

Where $H(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)$ is the Hamiltonian of the system. Therefore, by equating both expressions, we see that:

$$i\epsilon G(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t) = H(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)$$

That is, the observable associated with the time evolution generator has as its expectation value:

$$G(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t) = -\frac{i}{\epsilon} H(\vec{r}, \vec{p}, t)$$

It follows from this that everything indicates that the fifth postulate expresses the equivalence between both concepts. Before continuing, we will set $\epsilon = \hbar$ and will then briefly justify this using the starting equation. Moreover, we will refer to the system function as the wave function, which will also be justified later. The fifth postulate is then expressed as follows:

"The generator of time evolution is provided by the Hamiltonian operator, expressed as"

$$\hat{G}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}, t) = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{H}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}, t)$$

"With this, the smooth evolution of the system function can now be determined. To this end, we begin with equation (01), which serves as the evolution equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{G}|\psi(t)\rangle &= \frac{\partial|\psi(t)\rangle}{\partial t} \\ \Rightarrow \hat{H}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}, t)|\psi\rangle &= i\hbar \frac{\partial|\psi\rangle}{\partial t} \end{aligned}$$

By taking the bracket with $\langle \vec{r}, |$ on both sides, we obtain:

$$\langle \vec{r} | \hat{H}(\hat{R}, \hat{\Pi}, t) |\psi\rangle = i\hbar \langle \vec{r} | \frac{\partial|\psi\rangle}{\partial t} = i\hbar \frac{\partial(\langle \vec{r} | \psi \rangle)}{\partial t}$$

Assuming that the Hamiltonian is an arbitrary function that can be expressed as a Maclaurin power series, and applying the result of equation (16), we thus arrive at the Schrödinger equation for the wave functions:

$$\hat{H}(\hat{\vec{r}}, \hat{\vec{p}}, t) \psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$$

Here, the operators are given by:

$$\hat{\vec{r}} = \vec{r}I = (x_1I, \dots, x_NI)$$

$$\hat{\vec{p}} = -i\hbar\nabla = (-i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1}, \dots, -i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial x_N})$$

And the quantum Hamiltonian \hat{H} results from simply replacing the canonical variables with their operator representations indicated above:

Examples.

Case of a free particle with 3 degrees of freedom:

$$H = \frac{p_1^2}{2m} + \frac{p_2^2}{2m} + \frac{p_3^2}{2m}$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{H} = \frac{\hat{p}_1^2}{2m} + \frac{\hat{p}_2^2}{2m} + \frac{\hat{p}_3^2}{2m} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_3^2} \right)$$

With this, the differential equation is:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x_3^2} \right) = i\hbar\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t}$$

The case of one-dimensional motion under a general potential $V(x)$:

$$H = \frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x)$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{H} = \frac{\hat{p}^2}{2m} + V(\hat{x}) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + V(x)I$$

Thus, the differential equation is:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} + V(x)\psi = i\hbar\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t}$$

! Why $\epsilon = \hbar\omega$?

To answer this, it is enough to take the case of the free particle and obtain its general solution:

$$\psi = A_0 \exp(i(k_1x_1 + k_2x_2 + k_3x_3 - \omega t))$$

By substituting into the equation with ϵ , it holds that:

$$-\frac{\epsilon^2}{2m} (-k_1^2 - k_2^2 - k_3^2) = i\epsilon(-i\omega)$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\epsilon}{2m} |\vec{k}|^2 = \omega$$

From the findings of Planck and De Broglie, it is known that wave-particle duality is expressed as:

$$p = \frac{h}{\lambda}, \quad E = hf$$

As in the case of a free particle, the energy is purely kinetic; therefore:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} = E \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{h^2}{2m\lambda^2} = hf \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{h}{2m\lambda^2} = f$$

Multiplying both sides by $(2\pi)^2$ and noting that $|\vec{k}| = k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$, it follows that:

$$\frac{h}{2m}|\vec{k}|^2 = 2\pi f \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\hbar}{2m}|\vec{k}|^2 = \omega$$

From which it is evident that $\epsilon = \hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}$

Is a wave–particle duality really obtained?

This question is answered based on the concept of a function associated with a single particle. For any particle interacting with the rest of the system (whose total function is separable), its Hamiltonian can be described as:

$$H = \frac{p_1^2}{2m} + \frac{p_2^2}{2m} + \frac{p_3^2}{2m} + V(x_1, x_2, x_3)$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{H} = \frac{\hat{p}_1^2}{2m} + \frac{\hat{p}_2^2}{2m} + \frac{\hat{p}_3^2}{2m} + V(x_1, x_2, x_3) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_3^2} \right) + V(x_1, x_2, x_3)I$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{H} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(x_1, x_2, x_3)I$$

$$\Rightarrow -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + V(x_1, x_2, x_3)\psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$$

Taking its Hermitian part:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi^\dagger + V(x_1, x_2, x_3)\psi^\dagger = -i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi^\dagger}{\partial t}$$

Taking the first equation, we divide it by $i\hbar$ and multiply both sides by ψ^\dagger , yielding:

$$\Rightarrow -\frac{\hbar}{2mi} \psi^\dagger \nabla^2 \psi + \frac{1}{i\hbar} V(x_1, x_2, x_3)\psi^\dagger \psi = \psi^\dagger \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$$

Next, considering the second equation, dividing by $-i\hbar$ and multiplying by ψ , we obtain:

$$\frac{\hbar}{2mi} \psi \nabla^2 \psi^\dagger - \frac{1}{i\hbar} V(x_1, x_2, x_3)\psi \psi^\dagger = \psi \frac{\partial \psi^\dagger}{\partial t}$$

By adding them:

$$\frac{\hbar}{2mi} (\psi \nabla^2 \psi^\dagger - \psi^\dagger \nabla^2 \psi) = \psi^\dagger \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \psi \frac{\partial \psi^\dagger}{\partial t}$$

Since $\psi^\dagger \psi = |\psi|^2 = \rho$ is the probability density of locating the particle, the right-hand term is its partial derivative, as follows:

$$\frac{\hbar}{2mi} (\psi \nabla^2 \psi^\dagger - \psi^\dagger \nabla^2 \psi) = \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\hbar}{2mi} (\psi^\dagger \nabla^2 \psi - \psi \nabla^2 \psi^\dagger) + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = 0$$

Using a vector identity, it follows that:

$$\psi^\dagger \nabla^2 \psi = \nabla \cdot (\psi^\dagger \nabla \psi) - \nabla \psi^\dagger \cdot \nabla \psi$$

$$\psi \nabla^2 \psi^\dagger = \nabla \cdot (\psi \nabla \psi^\dagger) - \nabla \psi \cdot \nabla \psi^\dagger$$

Replacing:

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\hbar}{2mi} (\psi \nabla \psi^\dagger - \psi^\dagger \nabla \psi) \right) + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = 0$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{j} + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = 0$$

Here:

$$\vec{j} = \frac{i\hbar}{2m} (\psi \nabla \psi^\dagger - \psi^\dagger \nabla \psi) = \frac{\hbar}{m} \text{Im}(\psi^\dagger \nabla \psi)$$

This result confirms that the probability density is accompanied by a probability current density, implying that the system function effectively acts as a wave function, transmitting information about the particle via this density. Consequently, the wave function propagates through space while, in accordance with the correspondence principle, constraining the positional uncertainty to an almost negligible value, thereby recovering the apparent particle-like behavior with well-defined momentum and position. In other words, the wave function serves as an ideal tool for describing the dual nature of particles.

5. Conclusions

A formulation of Schrödinger quantum mechanics has been developed for Hamiltonians that are analytical functions, grounded on the first four postulates and extended by additional operational definitions. This framework naturally recovers fundamental structures such as the commutation relations between position and momentum, the unitary representation of translations and time evolution, and the emergence of expectation values consistent with classical observables due to the equivalence between commutators and Poisson brackets.

The analytical character of the Hamiltonian plays a central role, since it ensures the differentiability required for operator expansions and the validity of the canonical relations. It is therefore conjectured that Schrödinger quantum mechanics is, in essence, a theory intrinsically defined for analytical Hamiltonians, and that the inconsistencies or pathological behaviors arising in non-analytical systems may originate from extending the formalism beyond its natural analytical domain.

5. Annexes

5.1. Algebra in Hilbert spaces

A Hilbert space H is a complex vector space equipped with an inner product whose induced norm makes H a complete space.

Its elements are represented by a ket $|v\rangle \in H$ and the inner product is represented as $\langle u|v\rangle$ (that is, a product with the Bra $\langle u|$). For $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$, its properties are:

1. $\langle u|(v_1 + \lambda v_2)\rangle = \langle u|v_1\rangle + \lambda\langle u|v_2\rangle$
2. $\langle u_1 + \lambda u_2|v\rangle = \langle u_1|v\rangle + \bar{\lambda}\langle u_2|v\rangle$
3. $\overline{\langle u|v\rangle} = \langle v|u\rangle$
4. $\langle u_1|v\rangle = \langle u_2|v\rangle \quad \forall |v\rangle \Leftrightarrow |u_1\rangle = |u_2\rangle$
5. $\|u\| = \sqrt{\langle u|u\rangle}$ norm of a vector

The dual space of H is defined as H^* , consisting of functional operators $\langle A|: H \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, whose representation is given by:

$$\langle A||v\rangle = \langle A|v\rangle$$

These operators can be represented by an operator \hat{A} as follows:

$$|A\rangle = \hat{A}|v\rangle$$

That is, through the ket associated with the Bra $\langle A|$. Furthermore, the Hermitian conjugate \hat{A}^\dagger is defined as:

$$\langle u|\hat{A}^\dagger|v\rangle = \langle u|\hat{A}v\rangle \quad \forall |u\rangle, |v\rangle \in H$$

Based on this, the properties of the operators are as follows:

6. The identity operator is $I|v\rangle = |v\rangle \quad \forall |v\rangle \in H$
7. $\hat{A}^{-1}\hat{A} = \hat{A}\hat{A}^{-1} = I$
8. $(\hat{A}^\dagger)^\dagger = \hat{A}$
9. $(\hat{A}\hat{B})^\dagger = \hat{B}^\dagger\hat{A}^\dagger$
10. $(\lambda\hat{A} + \hat{B})^\dagger = \bar{\lambda}\hat{A}^\dagger + \hat{B}^\dagger$
11. If $\hat{A}^\dagger = \hat{A}$ then it is said that \hat{A} is Hermitian
12. If $\hat{A}|v\rangle = \lambda|v\rangle$ and \hat{A} is Hermitian, then $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$
13. The commutator between two operators is $[\hat{A}, \hat{B}] = \hat{A}\hat{B} - \hat{B}\hat{A}$
14. $[\hat{A}\hat{B}, \hat{C}] = \hat{A}[\hat{B}, \hat{C}] + [\hat{A}, \hat{C}]\hat{B}$
15. $[\hat{A}, \hat{B}\hat{C}] = \hat{B}[\hat{A}, \hat{C}] + [\hat{A}, \hat{B}]\hat{C}$

Finally, in a Hilbert space the Kronecker product is defined as:

$$\otimes : H \times H \rightarrow H \otimes H \quad / \quad \otimes (u, v) = u \otimes v$$

Where u, v can be elements of the Hilbert space $|u\rangle, |v\rangle$ or of the Hilbert dual space, that is, the operators \hat{U}, \hat{V} representing these dual elements.

Their properties are:

13. $(u_1 + u_2) \otimes v = u_1 \otimes v + u_2 \otimes v$
14. $u \otimes (v_1 + v_2) = u \otimes v_1 + u \otimes v_2$
15. $(u_1 \otimes v_1)(u_2 \otimes v_2) = (u_1 u_2) \otimes (v_1 v_2)$

5.2. Proof of the theorem presented in Section 3.7.1

We shall prove the general formula. The theorem is stated as follows:

Let $f(\hat{X})$ and $g(\hat{P})$ be functions with Maclaurin series, where \hat{X} and \hat{P} are the one-dimensional position and momentum operators, respectively; then:

$$\text{If } [\hat{X}, \hat{P}] = i\epsilon \quad \Rightarrow \quad [f(\hat{X}), g(\hat{P})] = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} f^{(k)}(\hat{X}) g^{(k)}(\hat{P})$$

Proof of the theorem:

As demonstrated in this work, it is established that $[\hat{X}, \hat{P}^n] = i\epsilon n \hat{P}^{n-1}$; therefore:

$$[\hat{X}, g(\hat{P})] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n [\hat{X}, \hat{P}^n] = i\epsilon \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n n \hat{P}^{n-1} = i\epsilon g^{(1)}(\hat{P})$$

Let see $[\hat{X}^2, g(\hat{P})]$

$$[\hat{X}^2, g(\hat{P})] = \hat{X}[\hat{X}, g(\hat{P})] + [\hat{X}, g(\hat{P})]\hat{X} = i\epsilon(\hat{X}g^{(1)}(\hat{P}) + g^{(1)}(\hat{P})\hat{X})$$

Since $[\hat{X}, g^{(1)}(\hat{P})] = \hat{X}g^{(1)}(\hat{P}) - g^{(1)}(\hat{P})\hat{X} = i\epsilon g^{(2)}(\hat{P}) \quad \Rightarrow \quad g^{(1)}(\hat{P})\hat{X} = \hat{X}g^{(1)}(\hat{P}) - i\epsilon g^{(2)}(\hat{P})$

Substituting and expanding accordingly:

$$[\hat{X}^2, g(\hat{P})] = 2(i\epsilon)\hat{X}g^{(1)}(\hat{P}) - (i\epsilon)^2 g^{(2)}(\hat{P})$$

Now let's see $[\hat{X}^3, g(\hat{P})]$

$$[\hat{X}^3, g(\hat{P})] = \hat{X}[\hat{X}^2, g] + [\hat{X}, g]\hat{X}^2 = \hat{X}(2i\epsilon\hat{X}g^{(1)} - (i\epsilon)^2 g^{(2)}) + i\epsilon g^{(1)}\hat{X}^2$$

Since $[\hat{X}^2, g^{(1)}(\hat{P})] = \hat{X}^2 g^{(1)} - g^{(1)}\hat{X}^2 = 2(i\epsilon)\hat{X}g^{(2)} - (i\epsilon)^2 g^{(3)}$

$$g^{(1)}\hat{X}^2 = \hat{X}^2 g^{(1)} - 2(i\epsilon)\hat{X}g^{(2)} + (i\epsilon)^2 g^{(3)}$$

Replacing

$$[\hat{X}^3, g(\hat{P})] = 3(i\epsilon)\hat{X}^2 g^{(1)} - 3(i\epsilon)^2 \hat{X}g^{(2)} + (i\epsilon)^3 g^{(3)}$$

The first three results may be expressed as follows:

$$[\hat{X}, g(\hat{P})] = \frac{(i\epsilon)}{1!} (\hat{X})^{(1)} g^{(1)}$$

$$[\hat{X}^2, g(\hat{P})] = \frac{(i\epsilon)}{1!} (\hat{X}^2)^{(1)} g^{(1)} - \frac{(i\epsilon)^2}{2!} (\hat{X}^2)^{(2)} g^{(2)}$$

$$[\hat{X}^3, g(\hat{P})] = \frac{(i\epsilon)}{1!} (\hat{X}^3)^{(1)} g^{(1)} - \frac{(i\epsilon)^2}{2!} (\hat{X}^3)^{(2)} g^{(2)} + \frac{(i\epsilon)^3}{3!} (\hat{X}^3)^{(3)} g^{(3)}$$

Inductive hypothesis:

$$[\hat{X}^n, g(\hat{P})] = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} (\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} g^{(k)}$$

$$[\hat{X}^{n+1}, g(\hat{P})] = \hat{X}^n [\hat{X}, g] + [\hat{X}^n, g] \hat{X} = \hat{X}^n (i\epsilon) g^{(1)} + \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} (\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} g^{(k)} \hat{X}$$

And since $\hat{X} g^{(k)} - g^{(k)} \hat{X} = (i\epsilon) g^{(k+1)} \Rightarrow g^{(k)} \hat{X} = \hat{X} g^{(k)} - (i\epsilon) g^{(k+1)}$, then:

$$[\hat{X}^{n+1}, g] = \hat{X}^n (i\epsilon) g^{(1)} + \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} (\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} \left(\hat{X} g^{(k)} - (i\epsilon) g^{(k+1)} \right)$$

$$[\hat{X}^{n+1}, g] = \underbrace{\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} (\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} \hat{X} g^{(k)}}_{\hat{S}_1} + \underbrace{i\epsilon \hat{X}^n g^{(1)} + \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+2} \frac{(i\epsilon)^{k+1}}{k!} (\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} g^{(k+1)}}_{\hat{S}_2}$$

Since $(\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} = n(n-1)\dots(n-k+1)\hat{X}^{n-k}$, then:

$$(\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} \hat{X} = n(n-1)\dots(n-k+1)\hat{X}^{n-k+1}$$

$$(\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} \hat{X} = (n+1-1)(n+1-2)\dots(n+1-k)\hat{X}^{(n+1)-k}$$

$$(\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} \hat{X} = \frac{(n+1)}{(n+1)} (n+1-1)(n+1-2)\dots(n+1-k+1)\hat{X}^{(n+1)-k} (n+1-k)$$

$$(\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} \hat{X} = \frac{(n+1-k)}{(n+1)} (\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k)} \quad (\text{para } \hat{S}_1)$$

And on the other hand $(\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k+1)} = (n+1)(n+1-1)\dots(n+1-(k+1)+1)\hat{X}^{n+1-(k+1)}$

$$\Rightarrow (\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k+1)} = (n+1)n(n-1)\dots(n-k+1)\hat{X}^{n-k} = (n+1)(\hat{X}^n)^{(k)}$$

$$\Rightarrow (\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} = \frac{1}{n+1} (\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k+1)} \quad (\text{para } \hat{\mathcal{S}}_2)$$

Replacing these results in both sums:

$$\hat{\mathcal{S}}_1 = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} (\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} \hat{X} g^{(k)} = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} \frac{(n+1-k)}{(n+1)} (\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k)} g^{(k)}$$

Since $n+1-k=0$ in $k=n+1$, then we extend the series to $k=n+1$:

$$\Rightarrow \hat{\mathcal{S}}_1 = \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} \frac{(n+1-k)}{(n+1)} (\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k)} g^{(k)}$$

$$\hat{\mathcal{S}}_2 = i\epsilon \hat{X}^n g^{(1)} + \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+2} \frac{(i\epsilon)^{k+1}}{k!} (\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} g^{(k+1)}$$

$$\hat{\mathcal{S}}_2 = i\epsilon \hat{X}^n g^{(1)} + \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+2} \frac{(i\epsilon)^{k+1}}{k!} \frac{1}{n+1} (\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k+1)} g^{(k+1)} \quad \text{changing } k \rightarrow k-1$$

$$\hat{\mathcal{S}}_2 = \underbrace{i\epsilon \hat{X}^n g^{(1)}}_{\frac{(-1)^{1+1} (i\epsilon)^1 (\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(1)} g^{(1)}}{(1-1)! n+1}} + \sum_{k=2}^{n+1} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{(k-1)!} \frac{(\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k)} g^{(k)}}{(n+1)}$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{\mathcal{S}}_2 = \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} k \frac{(\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k)} g^{(k)}}{n+1}$$

$$[\hat{X}^{n+1}, g] = \hat{\mathcal{S}}_1 + \hat{\mathcal{S}}_2 = \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} (n+1-k+k) \frac{1}{n+1} (\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k)} g^{(k)}$$

$$[\hat{X}^{n+1}, g] = \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} (\hat{X}^{n+1})^{(k)} g^{(k)}$$

This completes the proof. If $f(\hat{X})$ admits a power series expansion, i.e.:

$$f(\hat{X}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \hat{X}^n$$

$$[f(\hat{X}), g(\hat{P})] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n [\hat{X}^n, g] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} (a_n \hat{X}^n)^{(k)} g^{(k)}$$

Si $k > n \Rightarrow (\hat{X}^n)^{(k)} = 0 \Rightarrow$ the second series can be extended to $1 \leq k \rightarrow \infty$

$$\Rightarrow [f(\hat{X}), g(\hat{P})] = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} (a_n \hat{X}^n)^{(k)} g^{(k)}$$

$$\Rightarrow [f(\hat{X}), g(\hat{P})] = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} \underbrace{\left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (a_n \hat{X}^n)^{(k)} \right)}_{f^{(k)}(\hat{X})} g^{(k)}$$

$$\Rightarrow [f(\hat{X}), g(\hat{P})] = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} \frac{(i\epsilon)^k}{k!} f^{(k)}(\hat{X}) g^{(k)}(\hat{P})$$

References

- [1] Dirac, P. A. M. (1930). *The Principles of Quantum Mechanics*. Oxford University Press.
- [2] Eisberg, R., Resnick, R. (1974). *Quantum Physics of Atoms, Molecules, Solids, Nuclei, and Particles (2nd ed.)*. Wiley.
- [3] Fackler, S. (2015, 6 de mayo). *Mathematical Foundations of Quantum Mechanics* (versión de notas de curso). Universidad de Ulm.
- [4] Gasiorowicz, S. G. (2003). *Quantum Physics* (3rd ed.). Wiley.
- [5] Goldstein, H., Poole, C. P., & Safko, J. L. (2002). *Classical Mechanics* (3rd ed.). Addison-Wesley.
- [6] Levin, F. S. (2002). *An Introduction to Quantum Theory*. Cambridge University Press.
- [7] von Neumann, J. (1955). *Mathematical Foundations of Quantum Mechanics*. Princeton University Press.
- [8] Kragh, H. (1999). *Quantum Generations: A History of Physics in the Twentieth Century*. Princeton University Press.